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SEMANTCO

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1 Executive Summary

The purpose of the R&D conducted in the SEMANTCO project (www.semanco-project.eu) is to help architects, city planners, engineers, policy makers and citizens to reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions in towns and cities. To do so the project developed an integrated platform to provide access to widely dispersed energy related data about cities stored by many different organisations. In this way the project platform supports improved energy analysis based on the assessment of existing data rather than estimates. As such it integrates data from multiple domains (cadastre, Geographic Information Systems, socio-economic statistics) with energy assessment and analysis tools enabling users to:

- Develop urban energy models of cities and districts;
- Assess the current energy performance of buildings in those models;
- Develop new plans and projects to reduce urban energy demand;
- Set a baseline against which to measure the potential of different plans and projects to reduce urban energy demand;
- Conduct a multi-criteria analysis of the proposed solutions to identify the one that fits their policy or organisational aims most closely.

The integration of the data from the various sources (applications and domains), and the tools was achieved through the application of semantic technologies. At the core of the platform is the SEIF – Semantic Energy Information Framework, developed in the project. This framework provides the methods and tools to combine the data and to link the data to the tools. The semantic data modelling required the creation of an ontology, that is, an explicit representation of the concepts and relations between data. The SEMANTCO ontology contains the terms and attributes that describe regions, cities, neighbourhoods and buildings; energy consumption and CO₂ emission indicators, as well as climate and socio-economic factors that influence energy consumption. It is based on current energy standards, collated in ‘energy standards tables’ from which the terms of the ontology have been derived. The creation of the ontology also required the parallel development of specific tools to design it and to map it to the data sources. The SEMANTCO ontology and the methods and tools used to create it, are the significant ground breaking outcomes of the project.

The SEMANTCO platform is based on specifications derived from case studies conducted in Manresa (Spain), Newcastle (UK) and Copenhagen (Denmark). A methodology based on use case modelling, was developed and applied to identify strategic goals regarding carbon reduction in each case study area and the methods and tools required to achieve those goals. A use case encapsulates the data, tools and users required to address a particular question posed by stakeholders. Based on the use case descriptions, urban energy models have been created in the SEMANTCO platform for each of the three cases. The generic solution adopted in the structure of the platform facilitates its application to other cases beyond those considered in the project.

The platform and the tools that are included in it have been tested in iterative demonstrations implemented in parallel to the technological development of the project. Three iterations of the application of the methods and tools developed in the project to obtain feedback from users in different settings to fine-tune functionality of the SEMANTCO platform during its development. The findings from usability tests conducted in the final phases of the project demonstrated the effectiveness of the final release of the platform to facilitate qualified information to urban planners, policy makers, energy consultants and others experts.

After the end of the project, the exploitation of the project assets will be carried out through the energy service provider EECITIES (www.eecities.com). This customer oriented portal presents the functionalities of the SEMANTCO platform with a variety of communication material (videos, presentations and other documentation).

2 Summary Description

The quest to reduce carbon emissions in urban areas cannot be constrained to a particular geographical area or scale nor does it concern a particular discipline or an individual expert: it is a systemic problem which involves multiple scales and domains and the collaboration of experts from various fields. Considering the combined process of acquiring and using energy in an urban area as an urban energy system facilitates the understanding of the full complexity of the underlying problems. The application of semantic technologies can help to create models of urban energy systems by integrating the data from multiple domains, sources and applications, and facilitating access to this combined data to energy assessment and simulation tools. The goal of SEMANTCO has been to create an integrated platform which enables the creation of urban energy models with the purpose of analysing the energy performance of the buildings and to develop action plans to improve them.

Figure 1. Project approach

Thus the main purpose of the project is the implementation and evaluation of a platform to support the decision making of the different stakeholders involved in energy related urban planning at the neighbourhood, municipal and regional level. These tools are deployed throughout different stages in the lifecycle of buildings and places, from planning to daily building operation. The impact of these tools is evaluated by their application in case study scenarios in three urban areas, in Manresa (Spain), Newcastle (United Kingdom) and Copenhagen (Denmark). The platform will enable informed decisions to be made regarding the energy performance and cost effectiveness of different design and planning alternatives at the local, district and regional scales. The platform is applied to case study scenarios in order to demonstrate quantifiable and significant reductions in energy consumption and CO₂ emissions can be achieved.

SEMANTCO's approach to developing and integrating ICT tools to reduce CO₂ emissions is based on four interrelated components (Figure 1):

- Supporting access to, and analysis of, distributed and heterogeneous sources of energy related data;
- Semantic modelling of energy data, according to EU energy and ontology standards;
- Integrated tools, that access and update the semantically modelled data, based on new and existing IT solutions for decision making in the development of CO₂ reduction strategies;
- A requirements analysis to ensure that the tools and CO₂ reduction strategies developed address real world problems, within the SEMANTCO demonstration cases and throughout the EU.

Case study scenarios

The development of the platform is closely interwoven with three case study scenarios in Spain, United Kingdom and Denmark. These scenarios are instrumental to:

1. Identifying relevant indicators; interrelationships between factors contributing to CO₂ reduction; CO₂ emission reduction strategies; baselines for energy consumption; and uses of energy efficient and renewable energy technologies;
2. Verifying effectiveness of tools and methods; reductions of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions; social impact; improved indoor environmental qualities (IEQ); and investment costs.

The specific conditions of each case study are:

- **Manresa.** This case features an on-going urban redevelopment plan whose goal is to meet the sustainable development objectives set by the local authorities. The application of the platform tools can help building owners and occupants, managers of public buildings and local administrators to define strategies –at the political, technical and social levels– to reach those objectives.

- **Newcastle.** This city is in the process of developing and implementing a regeneration strategy for the west end of Newcastle which is one of the most deprived areas in the North East of England. The redevelopment includes the refurbishment and internal remodelling of dwelling configurations within three residential housing blocks. Local and national UK government bodies and social housing providers are involved in this case study.

- **Copenhagen.** This case focuses on the North Harbour, a new development project for which a master plan has been created. As part of the master plan an energy supply concept was developed showing the way to a CO₂ neutral city.

Different strategies will be adopted to evaluate the impact of the project outcomes in the specific areas of study, and to the different stakeholders involved in CO₂ reduction.

Integrated platform

A platform is developed consisting of: data repositories of energy related information structured according to existing standards; a Semantic Energy Information Framework; and a set of tools to interoperate with the semantic modelled data. The specifications for each of these three components of the platform can be summarized as follows:

- **Energy related data.** Different kinds of energy related data are collected from heterogeneous sources for each of the three scenarios. Energy data is disaggregated according to the level of urbanization, the building typology, the building equipment, the energy use, and the climatic features. Energy related data includes: location of buildings, building specifications – obtained through photogrammetric techniques–, weather data, site factors of energy load, electricity and gas consumption. Different types of energy data are collected at different scales (neighbourhood, municipal and regional): supply and consumption at the district/national level, pollution maps, district GIS maps of the urban environment, population/occupancy data and climate data, and energy consumption in buildings and neighbourhoods. Data sources are the repositories of data accessible only to project partners combined with Open Data available from public sources. Real data are complemented with statistical data wherever required.

- **Semantic Energy Information Framework.** A Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF) for modelling the energy performance of both domestic and commercial building stock at different geographical scales is developed to embody the energy-related knowledge planners need. The semantic mapping acts as a bridge between different domains (city planning and energy provision) and contents (consumption data, pollution sources, simulated energy profiles and benchmarks). This semantic model supports interoperability among systems by enabling translation and mapping between different modelling methods and tools to support decision making in urban planning. Through the SEIF, these tools access heterogeneous and distributed databases containing different types of energy related information semantically modelled which can be analysed in conjunction with data related to income, climate among others to help stakeholders place energy and CO₂ reduction planning within particular problem domains.

The semantic energy model (i.e. the SEMANTCO ontology) provides the vocabulary to express and interpret the complexity of different data sets and their interrelations. The semantic model acts as an information interchange enabling the tools developed in the project to link energy information throughout the different stages of the lifecycle of domestic and commercial building stock: that is design, construction, operation and retrofit. Requirements are identified for different types of users –mostly planners and energy consultants, but also non-experts such as social or public housing providers, facilities managers, building occupants, and community groups.

- **Integrated tools.** Tools interoperating with the semantic framework support the analysis of energy information at each lifecycle stage enabling stakeholders, such as policy makers, utility companies, planners, designers, engineers, consultants, energy service companies, energy distributors, facilities managers and building occupants, to make informed decisions about the energy performance and cost effectiveness of energy efficient and renewable energy interventions within particular contexts.

Existing tools for visualization, analysis, optimization are used and new tools are developed in order to collect, analyse and manage the information semantically modelled through the SEIF. The new tools are based on the correlation between data and the application of data-driven models. The tools integrated in the platform are:

- **Building stock energy modelling tool** that identifies and classifies domestic and non-domestic building stock using image recognition and map digitisation to automate the identification and classification of buildings at different geographical scales.
- **Energy information analysis tools** using data mining techniques enabling the transformation and analysis of multidimensional datasets to infer knowledge in the form of rules, inherent relations or classifications.
- **Energy simulation and trade-off visualisation** tools created using the GIS Platform 3DMaps from Agency9. The energy simulation tool will enable the identification of baseline energy emissions.
- An **interactive urban design** tool that enables planners to explore and evaluate different arrangements of buildings in project areas and evaluate their energy efficiency according to different parameters.

These tools are integrated in a platform that facilitates access to the semantic data to different stakeholders to assess and visualize the energy data and to operate with them.

Figure 2. Proposed integrated platform

In order to be able to use the platform developed as a decision tool it is important that it is both flexible and multi-dimensional so that data and presumptions can easily be changed to match both the actual baseline development in the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions of the urban environment and also give future forecasts if new energy efficient and renewable energy technologies are implemented in long-term development scenarios.

Exploitation plans

The main actors in the exploitation of the project results are expected to be industrial and consultant partners. The project addresses highly relevant aspects of structuring data and provision of tools to make qualified presentations of data as well as analysis for energy optimisation in sustainable urban planning. Customers for the solutions that may be derived from the project are potentially city or regional governments or private companies in power, real estate and energy sector. The business model may be in a form of a cloud service or licensed software. Furthermore the results and findings of SEMANTCO may open for new business opportunities in the form of information or consultancy services.

The tools and methods developed by the project could significantly pave the way towards sustainable development being an integral part of all urban planning projects as well as general spatial planning (regular updates of municipal codes etc.). Potential clients of such services include municipalities and city authorities, public and private city development companies, financing institutions, real estate companies and national energy authorities. These opportunities will be identified along the project implementation and actions will be taken to bring them into the market, in accordance with the exploitation plans to be developed in the project.

3 Scientific and Technical Results

The main goal of the SEMANTCO project has been the creation, development and implementation of a platform to integrate data from multiple sources, domains, scales and applications using semantic technologies. A set of energy assessment and analysis tools that operate with the combined data have been developed and included in the platform. The interaction with the tools and data provides urban planners, energy consultants and policy makers involved in the planning of energy efficient urban areas qualified information to support their decision making processes. The technological outputs of the project will be further disseminated and exploited through the EECITIES web portal (www.eecities.com).

The development of the platform has involved:

1. Analysing the requirements in each case study
2. Creating a shared vocabulary of energy standard concepts
3. Creating an ontology based on the shared vocabularies
4. Developing the platform and tools
5. Blending the technological development with the application of the platform in demonstration scenarios
6. Engaging stakeholders through the whole process, from requirement specifications, to platform design and testing

Along the process of development, the different results have been achieved in accordance with the scientific and technical objectives of the project.

The following sections described both the process followed in the project development and the results achieved.

3.1 Case study analysis requirement

According to the project work plan, the scope of the research was delimited by the case studies. This linked the research to real world scenarios at specific locations. The delimitation of the case studies took into consideration a) main international policy frameworks determining urban planning and the strategies for reducing CO₂ emissions, b) the national and local policy frameworks and urban planning schemes implemented in each of the demonstration sites, c) a preliminary list of relevant actors involved in the urban planning processes and the potential users of SEIF, d) a preliminary set of expected outcomes of the analytical tools developed, e) the data requirements, the available data and the data sources providing that information.

Following the discussions held within the SEMANTCO research team with regard to the notions of area and scale, a broad categorisation of spatial boundaries was adopted with the purpose of providing the necessary methodology required by the three case studies: micro, meso and macro scales. Likewise, the meaning of some terms used in the project was agreed:

- Data referred to energy-related open data, methods to the rules used to calculate the energy performance of buildings and places
- Tools are used to assess the energy performance of buildings and places and to support decision-making in urban planning
- Actors are stakeholders in the urban planning process who do not necessarily use tools
- Users are individuals who will be using the tools to calculate/simulate/visualise the energy performance of buildings and places

Monitoring of CO₂ emissions is also central to sustainable urban development. Therefore, urban planning schemes must include a monitoring strategy. Two strategic frameworks suggested by HEFCE (2010) and The International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives (ICLEI) in 1993, were consulted. Both strategic frameworks were considered valid for the project since they recommend the same approach, namely: defining a carbon reduction target, establishing a baseline, selecting relevant indicators, proposing a carbon reduction

implementation and management plan and defining a monitoring program. Subsequent to the above considerations relevant indicators for monitoring CO₂ emissions in urban planning were structured according to the following categories: indicator type, unit, extensive/intensive, calculation method, inputs required, key questions addressed in the use case, benchmark description and score.

A total of 62 indicators dealing with these issues were identified and described²: a) Energy demand for final energy uses, b) Demand for different energy carriers, c) Energy distribution losses, d) Energy carriers from renewable energy sources, e) Renewable energy in the total electricity supply, f) Share of local electricity carriers from renewable energy sources, g) Share of local energy carriers from renewable energy sources, h) CO₂ emissions and reduction compared to baseline, i) Energy simulations in buildings, j) Costs/Economics, and k) Fuel poverty.

The relevance of the different indicators has been explained and wherever a formula is required to calculate an indicator, it is suggested. Certain parameters of an indicator may be specific to a country. Therefore, each case study provided a local methodology/formula to calculate the indicator when necessary. However, the indicators listed do not distinguish between countries, nor are they restricted to a specific scale (e.g. neighbourhood, city, municipal, regional) since it is assumed that the indicators developed are addressing the key questions and strategies related to energy efficient urban development and reduced CO₂ emissions at all scales and in all countries (at least at the European level).

A methodology and process of defining indicators has been implemented. The methodology of defining indicators was done in the following steps : a) Identification of key questions (from policy frameworks, urban planning objectives etc.), b) Identification of relevant flows (energy carriers, energy losses, CO₂ emissions, costs etc.), c) Definition of relevant indicator types, d) Definition of indicator list.

The choice of indicators has been based on the use of fund and flow categories as proposed by the MuSIASEM approach. These indicators deal with carbon emissions, use of energy carriers, primary energy and costs. The effects of carbon emissions are implicitly given. Therefore, once the indicators were defined, an implementation plan was described in the following terms: “Description of measurement parameters, indicators of success, contingency plans and key control points in the process for each of the 3 case studies to enable subsequent control and evaluation of implementation, international comparability and know-how sharing.”

Use case methodology

The use case methodology adopted from the start of the project has underpinned the subsequent project development (Figure 3). A use case brings together the data, tools and users required to address a particular question posed by stakeholders. It comprises a series of activities, namely, specific actions which have to be performed to fulfil a task within a use case.

Figure 3. The use case definition as nexus between case studies and platform development

² Hvid, J., Ennis, C. (eds) (2012). SEMANCO Deliverable 2.2 *Strategies and Indicators for Monitoring CO₂ Emissions*. Retrieved January 30, 2015 at http://www.semanco-project.eu/index_htm_files/SEMANCO_D2.2_20121015.pdf

The use cases have been elaborated at the start of the project, in a joint work which has involved domains experts and ontology designers. The use case description is a generic statement of a complex problem dealing with carbon reduction in urban planning which require a series of discrete actions to be undertaken which are referred as activities (Figure 4).

Figure 4. A Use case and its activities

Use cases can make a network in the sense that the output of a use case can serve as input for another (Figure 5). The arrows in the figure indicate that the output of one use case or activity is the input of another one.

Figure 5. Activities (in green boxes), data requirements and expected outputs

Use cases and their activities are described by means of templates specifically developed in the project. A use case template contains the following information:

- *Acronym*: Use Case number
- *Goal*: explain the goal of the use case
- *Super-Use case*: specify the super-use cases which contain this use case
- *Sub-Use Case* : specify the sub-use cases contained in this use case
- *Work Process*: select the domain in which the work process is carried out (planning, design, performance)
- *Users*: describe users involved in the use case (i.e. planners, architects, citizens, policy makers etc.)
- *Actors*: identify stakeholders and explain why reaching the goal is important for them
- *Related national/local policy framework*: identify national/local policy frameworks related to the use

- case
- *Activities*: list the Activities involved in the use case

In turn, the activities template includes:

- *Acronym*: Activity number
- *Super-Activity/Use Case*: specify the super-activities or use cases which contain this activity
- *Sub-Activities*: specify the sub-activities contained in this activity
- *Goal*: explain the goal of the Activity. Add in the goal of the calculation method to be used (detailed, simplified, energy balance)
- *Urban scale*: select one or more scales (micro, meso or macro).
- *Users*: select one or more users from the related use case
- *Issues to be addressed*: describe the issues to be addressed to carry out the activity.
- *Method*: explain the method applied to transform input data into output data. It is related to the data flow of the related use case

The methodology to model use cases and create an urban energy model devised, applied and validated in this project can be considered one of its major outcomes. This methodology can be used to create additional urban energy models and be replicated in other domains and contexts. Overall, fourteen use cases were defined following the use case methodology outlined above in the three case studies³. For each use case, activities to perform the task were defined. Then, the activities of the different use cases were linked to make a network of activities cutting across the use cases.

The process to define the preliminary set of use cases began with a series of meetings with relevant stakeholders. These stakeholders were considered potential users of the tools developed by SEMANTCO. The meetings focused on exploring and identifying the requirements of future users while identifying relevant use cases. After the identification and definition of the use cases, it followed the difficult task of translating them into a sequence of activities and data flows which would be then applied in various contexts as prescribed in the demonstration scenarios

One of the fourteen use cases was selected to design the demonstration scenarios to be implemented in the three case studies. Its goal was defined in these terms: “To calculate the energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, costs and /or socio-economic benefits of an urban plan for a new or existing development”. Figure 6 shows the sequence of activities encompassed in this use case.

Figure 6. Sequence of activities of a use case

³ Cipriano, X., Gamboa, G., Pérez, D. (eds.) (2012) SEMANTCO Deliverable 8.1 *Implementation Plan (Appendix B)*. Retrieved January 30, 2015 at http://www.semanco-project.eu/index_htm_files/SEMANTCO_D8.1_20121015.pdf

The use cases were further developed in the design of the demonstration scenarios. They provided a common methodology to capture the common issues involved in the energy assessment process at each country.

The work described in this section has contributed to achieve the following scientific and technological objectives:

- STO1 Developing evidence-based quantifiable strategies to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions through ICTs situated within their particular problem domain.

The complexities and challenges entailed by the definition of the analytical scales has been acknowledged and, accordingly, an accounting framework has been devised to perform energy related assessments across scales and dimensions. This framework enables to track the different forms of energy flows and to calculate adequate performance indicators in order to identify ‘energy use hot spots’.

- STO8 Demonstrate and validate the value of decision support tools in terms of their cost effectiveness and ability to support informed planning decisions that reduce CO₂ emissions from the built environment. This demonstration and validation phase of the research will be conducted in specifically designed scenarios with the end-users within the case studies

Valid and useful indicators like the SAP rate used in the UK or intensity energy demand in Spain (kWh/m²•yr), CO₂ emissions, and energy consumption have been applied to help planners in the decision making process. Additionally, more indicators can be proposed by the users to evaluate measures to improve the existing environmental conditions. Stakeholders other than planners can also work with the proposed indicators like those concerning supply technology in terms of energy demand, CO₂ emissions and energy cost, and add complementary indicators. However some socio-economic indicators, such as population density, or internal rate of return (IRR) have not been considered.

- STO9 Develop generalised guidelines and recommendations which can be widely applied within urban planning and redevelopment projects

A framework is proposed to track energy flows, calculate performance indicators and identify ‘energy use hot spots’. The challenges of energy analysis at different geographic scales are addressed. Different strategies are proposed to assess the efficacy of energy efficient measures taking into account technical, demographic and socio-economic factor.

3.2 Energy standard vocabularies

Building ontologies to describe urban energy systems require the standardisation of terms and units of measures and the application of a universally recognised terminology that is accepted by the community. From the 14 use cases created from the analysis of the case studies, an informal vocabulary of the terms used in their description was jointly produced by domain experts and ontology engineers. The terms of the vocabulary were based on international technical standards and on the recognized terminology accepted by the community and were compiled in the *Energy Standard Tables*.

The *Energy Standard Tables* stand for the informal vocabulary which precedes the construction of the formal vocabulary, that is, the ontology (Corrado, Ballarini, Madrazo & Nemirovski, 2015)⁴. The diagram presented in Figure 7 shows the role of the *Energy Standard Tables* in the overall ontology design process.

⁴ Corrado, V., Ballarini, I., Madrazo, L., Nemirovski, G. (2015) Data structuring for the ontological modelling of urban energy systems: The experience of the SEMANTCO project. In *Journal of Sustainable Cities and Society*, Volume 14, Pages 223-235 (in press).

Figure 7. Role of the Energy Standard Tables in the process of information and knowledge capturing

The *Energy Standard Tables* act as a connection between the available information (e.g. in the form of permanently stored data) and the knowledge of experts as expressed in technical standards and use case specifications. Therefore, these tables stand for a conceptualisation of an interdisciplinary domain (i.e. an urban energy system) by providing the definition of the terms which experts consider to be relevant to the problem at stake as well as the relationships between concepts.

Before starting the informal vocabulary building and the construction of the *Energy Standard Tables*, the data were collected from use cases and classified in categories, i.e. “Energy data”, “Climatic data”, “Building technical data”, “Energy cost data”, “Environmental data”, “Legislative constraints”, “Geographical data”, “Land and buildings registry data”, “Urban planning data”, “Socio-economic data”, “Demographic data”. In order to perform an ontological modelling of data at different territorial scales, each data category was referred to a well-defined area (i.e. country, region, municipality, neighbourhood, and building).

The terms used in the *Energy Standard Tables* have been derived from existing technical standards (ISO and CEN standards), European projects and international official classifications. These sources supply the proper terminology, the descriptions, the relationships between concepts and, if applicable, the symbols and the units of the defined quantities. In particular, technical standard are the means by which experts agree on a common vocabulary in a particular domain. The harmonization of the language used by different experts is a prerequisite for the subsequent construction of the formal shared vocabulary (i.e. the ontology).

The *Energy Standard Tables* are implemented as a set of spreadsheets, where the terminology, descriptions, units of measures and relationships between concepts are described. Concepts are structured according to two components, objects and attributes. An object specifies what the concept “is”; an attribute is a property of the concept (i.e. what the concept “has”). According to these rules, which are the foundations of formal concept analysis, the *Energy Standard Tables* were elaborated by including a concept (datum) in each row of a spreadsheet and by prepending the “is” (subsumption) or “has” (attribute) field to each datum name. Information is provided for each concept in different columns, as follows:

- the datum name or the acronym, which can be made of different words separated by underscores;
- the description of the concept, which is obtained from the official reference (technical standards, projects, classifications, etc.);
- the reference that provides the description;
- the type of datum, whether descriptive (e.g. string, logic), or numeric (e.g. integer, real);
- the unit, if applicable;
- the name of other *Energy Standard Tables* (sheets), in which that concept is further detailed (identification of relationships with other concepts).

An example of the *Energy Standard Table* structuring the “building” concept is shown in Figure 8.

At the end of the SEMANCO project, a total number of 25 *Energy Standard Tables* were produced, covering different domains (i.e. data categories) and encompassing 987 concepts, which have been included in the ontology. A high quantity of data is accessed through the SEIF, including the data generated by the tools integrated in the SEMANCO platform.

The *Energy Standard Tables* were used to create urban energy models in the three case studies (Manresa, Copenhagen and Newcastle) using the SEMANCO integrated platform. To create these models, it was necessary to link the concepts (i.e. terms) of the *Energy Standard Tables* to the available data sources. In particular:

- In the urban model of Manresa, 16 domains were defined using the terms of the *Energy Standard Tables* (“Territory”, “Land”, “Climate”, “Housing”, “Population”, “Building”, “Building system”, “Energy quantities”, “Energy generator”, “C.S. geometry”, “C.S. envelope”, “C.S. internal partitions”, “C.S. occupancy”, “C.S. indoor air temperature”, “C.S. internal heat gains”, “TIME”) and 87 concepts were applied.
- In Newcastle, 13 domains were included (“Territory”, “Land”, “Housing”, “Population”, “Building”, “Building system”, “C.S. geometry”, “C.S. envelope”, “C.S. ventilation”, “C.S. internal partitions”, “C.S. occupancy”, “C.S. internal heat gains”, “TIME”) and 39 concepts used.
- Finally, 9 domains were integrated in the urban model of Copenhagen (“Territory”, “Land”, “Building”, “Building system”, “Energy quantities”, “Energy generator”, “Energy refurbishment”, “Requirement related to energy”, “Cost related to energy”) and 22 concepts applied.

Name/Acronym		Description	Reference	Type of data	Unit	Reference to other sheets
Building		construction as a whole, including its envelope and all technical building systems, for which energy is used to condition the indoor climate, to provide domestic hot water and illumination and other services related to the use of the building	EN 15603	-	-	-
has	Building_Name	name (ID) of the building	-	string	-	-
has	Age	construction period of the building	-	string	-	-
is	Year_Of_Construction	year of construction of the building	-	string	-	-
is	Age_Class	period of years to be defined according to typical construction or building properties (materials, construction principles, building shape, ...)	TABLLA	string	-	-
	has	From_Year	TABLLA	string	-	-
	has	To_Year	TABLLA	string	-	-
	has	Allocation	TABLLA	string	-	-
	has	Identifier	SLMO	A,B,C,D	-	-
has	Building_Use	use of the building	-	string	-	"b_use"
has	Building_Geometry	geometry of the building	-	-	-	-
has	Number_Of_Complete_Storeys	number of floors/storeys of the building	TABLLA*	integer	-	-
has	Basement	usable part of a building that is situated partly or entirely below ground level	EN ISO 13370	string	-	-
has	Number_Of_Apartments	number of apartments of the building	TABLLA	integer	-	-
has	Space	enclosed space within a building	ANSI/ASHRAE 90.1	string	-	-
is	Conditioned_Space	heated and/or cooled space	EN 15603 EN ISO 13790	string	-	-
has	CS_Geometry	geometry of the conditioned space of the building	ANSI/ASHRAE 90.1	-	-	"cs_geometry"
has	CS_Envelope	the exterior plus semi-exterior portions of a building (separating conditioned space from external environment or from unconditioned space)	ANSI/ASHRAE 90.1*	-	-	"cs_envelope"
has	CS_Internal_Partitions	portions of a building within the conditioned space	-	-	-	"cs_internal_partitions"
has	CS_Occupancy	characteristics of the conditioned space occupancy	-	-	-	"cs_occupancy"
has	CS_Indoor_Air_Temperature	arithmetic average of the air temperature and the mean radiant temperature at the centre of a zone or conditioned space	EN ISO 13790*	-	-	"cs_indoor_air_temperature"
has	CS_Ventilation	characteristics of the ventilation of the conditioned space	-	-	-	"cs_ventilation"
has	CS_Internal_Heat_Gains	heat provided within the building by occupants (sensible metabolic heat) and by appliances such as domestic appliances, office equipment, etc., other than energy intentionally provided for heating, cooling or hot water preparation	EN ISO 13790	-	-	"cs_internal_heat_gains"
has	Energy_Quantity_Related_To_Conditioned_Space	energy referred to building conditioned space	-	-	-	"energy_quantities"

Figure 8. Example of the Energy Standard Table structuring the “building” concept (extract)

Figure 9. Energy Standard Tables and their connections

The methodology to use the *Energy Standard Tables* in the ontology has proved to be an effective one to design the ontology. The ontology enabled semantic tools to access the data stemming from different domains and applications. The construction of the *Energy Standard Tables* is a multidisciplinary process in itself, since it involved the collaboration of ontology engineers and domain experts working together in the task of re-defining the terms facilitated by experts using the vocabulary of the technical standards (Figure 9). An effective collaboration is necessary to ensure a successful application of the ontology for solving a particular problem related to a specific policy framework.

In the process of building the *Energy Standard Tables*, it was necessary to dedicate considerable efforts to eliminate contradictions and inconsistencies between different standards. Hence, this research work can be also considered as a step forward towards further standardization in the urban energy system domain. As the standards concerning the urban domain are in the process of being developed and updated, the concepts in the *Energy Standard Tables* are not unmovable, but they will need a continuous review and updating in the next years.

The terms and definitions included in the *Energy Standard Tables* can be enhanced in the future as a result of new applications. The vocabulary provided in the *Energy Standard Tables* can be used to model other cases that deal with the modelling of urban energy systems at various scales.

The *Energy Standard Tables* are published via the SEMANCO website in form of pdf files. They are public and open source data for the research community. As regards the licensing terms for use outside the SEMANCO project, the actual *Energy Standard Tables* in Excel file are available upon request without charge through nominative delivery.

The work described in this section has contributed to achieve the following scientific and technological objectives:

- STO2 Structuring energy related data held in distributed repositories in heterogeneous formats according to the Open Data initiative and the ISO standards. This will enable an analysis of the complex correlations between the factors determining CO₂ production.

The Energy Standard Tables have enabled to construct an ontology which facilitates access to the contents of disperse data sources. They are part of a methodology to conceptualize multidisciplinary domains using ontologies. The tables encapsulate the knowledge gathered from existing technical standards to create the basis for a shared language among the various experts involved in the definition of an urban energy model.

- STO9 Develop generalised guidelines and recommendations which can be widely applied within urban planning and redevelopment projects.

The standardisation of terms and units of measures and the application of a universally recognised terminology contributed to develop the methodology for building energy models and integrating data through semantic technologies. That methodology is a relevant asset for developing systems to support urban planning and redevelopment projects since it can be replicated in other scenarios with other kinds of

data sources and user requirements. The methodology, together with the tools developed to support it, is a clear progression beyond the state of the art.

3.3 Ontology

Semantic technologies have been used to integrate data from different domains, scales, sources and applications, and to facilitate the access to these data to the energy assessment and analysis tools provided by the platform. The Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF) developed within SEMANTCO project is a key technological component and one of the central components of the entire SEMANTCO platform. The main goal of the SEIF is to facilitate the energy assessment and analysis tools integrated within the SEMANTCO platform the access to the distributed data sources that hold the data they require. The SEIF is made of the following components: an ontology, a methodology for its development, a federation engine (Elite), ontology editor, mapping tools, and semantic data explorer.

The SEMANTCO Energy Model

The SEMANTCO Energy Model constitutes the core of the SEIF. It is a formal ontology – specified using Web Ontology Language 2 (OWL 2) – comprising concepts captured from diverse sources including standards, use cases and activity descriptions and data sources related to the domains of urban planning and energy management. In particular, it contains the terms and attributes that describe regions, cities, neighbourhoods and buildings; energy consumption and CO₂ emission indicators, as well as climate and socio- economic factors that influence energy consumption. The ontology enables semantic tools to access the data stemming from different domains and applications.

The most relevant contribution of this semantic energy model is that it combines ontology design with the integration of data sources into one single process. This methodology explicitly requires formal and informal mappings of data sources vocabularies and an evaluation of the ontology by means of querying data sources managed by this ontology.

The semantic energy model is one of the first implemented ontologies using the DL-Lite_A formalism. The experience of its application must be of high value for the group of researchers working on data integration using semantic technologies. Moreover, the concepts underlying the applied methodology for ontology design go beyond the state of the art. To our knowledge, a methodology combining ontology design with data integration techniques, such as formal and informal mapping of data sources vocabularies and query design, has not been applied before.

The SEMANTCO energy model is being used and extended in several research projects among them OPTIMUS (<http://www.optimus-smartcity.eu/>) of 7th Framework Programme.

Ontology building process

In general, an ontology design process requires a methodological approach to avoid redundant work, to reduce design errors, and to be replicable in other contexts. The SEMANTCO project has been developed a unique ontology design methodology based on the use case elaboration (Nemirovski, Nolle, Sicilia, Ballarini & Corrado, 2013)⁵. This methodology is summarized in Figure 10. It starts with a description of use cases and activities that are single components of the use cases describing users, their goals and data required to achieve these goals. At the next step energy standard tables containing the terms and definitions of the vocabulary are extracted from the activity descriptions. The Energy Standard Tables serve as an immediate semi-formal source for the coding of the ontology. Parallel to this process, the data sources related to the use cases are identified and their schemas are mapped to the terms of the energy standard tables. Finally, the mapping of the ontology entities onto the elements of data sources schemas are created to facilitate querying of the data contained in this sources and transformation of this data into Resource Description Framework (RDF) -format.

⁵ Nemirovski G., Nolle A., Sicilia Á. Ballarini I. & Corrado V. (2013). Data integration driven ontology design, case study smart city. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Web Intelligence, Mining and Semantics*, pages 1–10.

Figure 10. The processes and methods employed to build the SEMANTCO ontology

The goal of the process outlined above has been twofold: to design a semantic energy model as a formal ontology and to integrate data sources by reorganising them according to the ontology structure. The resulting semantic energy model is a formal ontology embracing the terminology and relations needed to integrate the data sources and query them in a unified way. This way, the semantic integration process converts the data sources to RDF in accordance with the ontology.

In the following sections the six main tasks involved in the ontology building process are explained and the outcomes achieved are described.

1. *Vocabulary capture.* The first task of the ontology design process is to capture the base terminology for the ontology, that is to say, to make the knowledge that domain experts have about the issues related to a use case explicit. By means of use cases, experts describe how actors, tools, and data relate to each other in order to fulfil a specific goal under a specific policy framework. The activities encompassed by a use case are described in form of requirements and competency. This way, the data sources required to carry out the activities are identified and briefly described.
2. *Building an initial vocabulary.* In the second task, the use cases and activity specifications are analysed with the goal to define an initial vocabulary. This is a categorised set of terms connected by simple relations such as subsumption (is) and aggregation (has). To build the initially vocabulary it is necessary to identify the data categories, to scrutinise the existing international standards for energy modelling and to create energy standard tables, which are a set of semantically structured terms, including objects, attributes and standard definitions. The initial vocabulary is composed of 24 categories including building use, climate and building geometry. Around 1000 terms were collected including; descriptions, references, units, and type of data. 18 standards (e.g. ISO/IEC CD 13273-1, ISO/IEC CD 13273-2, EN 15603 and the EN ISO 15927-1) and 16 references (e.g. research project, public recommendations, European directives) were used to create the energy standard tables.
3. *Mapping data sources to vocabularies.* The goal of the third task is to map the data entities of the data sources –identified in the activities of the use cases– to the initial vocabulary. If a target data source is a relational database, then the fields of their tables are mapped to the terms of the initial vocabulary. The mappings are specified by data owners and domain experts using a table template. Nine different data sources have been mapped to the initial vocabulary including census and cadastre records, building typologies, neighbourhoods, energy coefficients among others. In total, more than 60 mappings are established between the data entities of the data sources and the initial vocabulary.
4. *Ontology coding.* The fourth task is focused on the codification of the semantic energy model, as a formal ontology based on the DL-LiteA formalism which outperforms most other description logic formalisms when managing data distributed in heterogeneously structured sources. The coding of the semantic energy model is carried out by SEMANTCO’s ontology editor. Following a modular approach

to ontology design, the semantic energy model is built with modules of the Suggested Upper Merged Ontology (SUMO). In this way, each concept of the semantic energy model is subsumed at least by one concept of SUMO. SUMO was selected, rather than DOLCE, PROTON, General Formal Ontology (GFO), and Basic Formal Ontology (BFO) because of its simplicity of understanding, applicability for reasoning and inference purposes, the ability to apply units of measurement to data, and the number of concepts it contains related to the urban planning domain. The outcome of this task is the creation of a global ontology based on the SUMO upper-ontology encompassing 592 concepts and 468 relations implemented with 3459 axioms in DL-LiteA style.

5. *Mapping data sources.* The aim of this task is to apply the informal mappings produced in the previous task to transform the contents of the data sources into RDF resources. After coding the mappings, using a formal language of a dedicated middleware, the data stored in relational databases becomes available for SPARQL querying in terms of the target global ontology. These mappings are implemented with declarative mapping languages such as R2RML, which offer rich expressive features helping to adjust rigid relational schemas to real cases. As a result of this task, 9 data sources have been semantically integrated using more than 400 mappings automatically generated by the ontology mapping tool. More than 3 million RDF triples have been generated in total.
6. *Evaluation.* In this task the quality of the ontology created in the previous stages of the process is evaluated. In particular, three properties have been evaluated: intelligibility that is the ability of experts that use the ontology to understand the ontology structure; mapping compliance ensuring the complete correspondence of the mapping with the ontology; and computational efficiency regarding the ability of the ontology to support conjunctive querying on high efficiency level, for example, with a comparatively short response time. The intelligibility test was carried out at the early stages of the ontology development, with two independent groups of users: a group of computer science students and another made up of experts in the field of building energy. The positive scores obtained in the test were 97.30% for computer science students and 91.20% for domain experts.

Tools developed within the project

In order to carry out the ontology design process outlined above, it has been necessary to develop specific tools which were not available to the ontology designers at the start of the project: a user-friendly ontology editor to visualize and edit the ontologies (Click-On), a federated query engine to automatically look-up to the data sources linked to the ontology (ELITE), a collaborative ontology mapping environment that helps domains experts and ontology engineers to integrate the data (Map-On), and collaborative environment to enable the exploration of the integrated data to multiple users (Search-On). These tools are accessible to the research community in the portal www.semanco-tools.eu.

- **Click-On** is an ontology editor developed as a tool for cooperative ontology design, involving ontology designers and domain experts, such as building engineers and energy consultants (Wolters, Nemirovski & Nolle, 2013)⁶. It hides the complexity of coding ontologies in DL-LiteA formalism, facilitating the collaboration between ontology engineers and domain experts. This editor offers to the user two simultaneous views of an ontology: one for editing the taxonomy of concepts, and another one for editing the graph of non-subsumption relations. A user can generate new concepts by editing both views. The SEMANTCO ontology editor, as most of currently available ontology editors, does not support free code editing in terms of XML code.

The SEMANTCO ontology editor addresses the following three requirements typical for the ontology design in the context of ontology based data integration.

Supporting collaborative ontology design. In the praxis a crucial task of ontology design projects is to assure correspondences between the formal assertions in the ontology code and the application domain knowledge that is usually expressed informally. Domain experts who are the carriers of this knowledge often lack the skills of formal knowledge representation, while ontology engineers lack the application domain knowledge.

⁶ Wolters, M., Nemirovski, G., & Nolle, A. (2013). ClickOn A: An Editor for DL-Lite A based Ontology Design. *Proceedings of the 26th International Workshop on Description Logics*, volume 1014 of CEUR, ceur-ws.org, pages 1000–1010.

In this context the SEMANTCO ontology editor on one hand restricts the number of design patterns used in an ontology and facilitates specification of these patterns in highly interactive manner.

Supporting design of ontologies for data integration. The SEMANTCO ontology editor facilitates specification of ontologies using the *DL-Lite_A* formalism, that especially addresses to the requirements of ontology based data integration. SEMANTCO ontology editor limits generation of the OWL code to the elements available in *DL-Lite_A*. Such limitation is achieved by providing to the user a finite set of GUI widgets, like context menu options. Each of these options generates, deletes or modifies an OWL code corresponding to a particular *DL-Lite_A* element.

Facilitating Ontology Evaluation. In order to involve domain experts into the process of ontology evaluation the SEMANTCO ontology editor facilitates an ontology representation that reveals the implications which may not be obvious for domain experts faintly familiar with formal logics. To do so - instead of visualizing TBox assertions per se – the editor visualizes the result of a TBox interpretation including all borderline cases, like possible equivalence of concepts on the right- and left-hand in a subsumption axiom. To achieve high usability and optimized ontology authoring it is important that users are able to navigate through both inferred graphs (taxonomy and the properties graph) in a most natural and transparent way. In this context Click-On offers the following settings:

All nodes of the ontology graph are coloured with regard to their meaning (the legend on the control panel explains the different colours)

- Mouse click navigation: After a concept is clicked on with the left mouse button it is going to be centred on the screen and relations originating from the corresponding graph node and (optionally) form its sub nodes become visible. Double clicking on a node results in a new tree presentation where the selected concept becomes the root of a taxonomy.
- Enlarging or collapsing parts of the ontology graph by a zoom function
- Controlling the tree depth (one, two or three levels can be displayed simultaneously)
- Changing graph direction from e. g. left to right or bottom down
- Forward and backward navigation within a selection history

- **ELITE** is a federated query engine that facilitates a complete and transparent querying of distributed autonomous data sources, for example relational databases or triple stores (Nolle & Nemirovski, 2013)⁷. **ELITE** uses SPARQL queries that refer to an ontology which is univocally mapped onto the schemas of data sources. At runtime the queries are translated into the query language (usually SQL) comprehensible for the data sources. This approach simplifies the query design as long as the end-user does not have to know how the physical data layer is organized, formatted, and structured.

The query rewriting and execution is controlled by a semantic index look up procedure that helps to identify data available at each single federated data source. The query answers provided by these sources are fused and delivered to the application which has formulated the original query. In other words ELITE can be seen as a virtual semantic data base that provides a homogeneous querying procedure to data physically stored at different locations and aligned at different schema. For the end user ELITE hides the complexity of the querying process.

From the technical point of view ELITE combines several different technologies. It makes use of Ontology based data access (OBDA) techniques that facilitate query rewriting. On the one hand SPARQL to SPARQL, by taking into account the preselected entailment regimes and by these means to guarantee completeness and soundness of query answers. On the other hand SPARQL to SQL to enable accessing of relational data sources. Besides that, ELITE supports highly efficient query processing by means of an improved implementation of R-Tree-based indexing.

⁷ Nolle A., Nemirovski G. (2013). ELITE: An Entailment-Based Federated Query Engine for Complete and Transparent Semantic Data Integration. *Proceedings of the 26th International Workshop on Description Logics*, volume 1014 of CEUR, ceur-ws.org, pp. 854–867.

Apart of its direct use as a central SPARQL end-point service for virtual data bases, ELITE can be applied for evaluation of consistency in distributed data repositories.

- **Map-On** is a collaborative ontology mapping environment helps different users –domain experts, data owners, and ontology engineers– to integrate data in a collaborative way using standard semantic technologies. The tools also automate parts of the semantic integration process in Ontology-based data access (OBDA) scenarios. In particular, with this tool it is possible:

- Loading multiple SQL database schema in the environment and their visual representation.
- Loading multiple ontologies, in particular those written in DL-LiteA formalism and their visual representation.
- Manual mapping the database to a domain ontology.
- Automatic generating of R2RML statements such as:
 - URI patterns (i.e. subjectMap and objectMap)
 - SQL queries (i.e. sqlQuery)

The tool has been validated through their application in the data integration process of the SEMANTCO project. However, the prototype tool is generic enough to be applied to other OBDA scenarios where R2RML mappings have to be generated by non-technical-skilled users. In the SEMANTCO project, a semantic integration process were carried out to incorporate data sources into Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF) which contains a global ontology embracing all the terms which the tools need to interact with the SEIF. The ontology mapping tool we have developed enables users to follow the steps of the integration process.

The process is based on the ontology-based data access paradigm where the data is accessed by means of a domain ontology. The goal of the process is to generate the mappings between the data source and the ontology. The mappings are coded in R2RML language. Since all data sources are mapped to the same domain ontology the ELITE engine can invoke federated queries using the same ontology.

- The **Search-On** environment has been designed as an interface –based on Semantic Web technologies– to enable domain experts and ontology engineers to explore the data accessible over a SPARQL endpoint. This environment reduces the complexity of using the semantic technologies by hiding the ontology constructs by means of an easy to use interface based on semi natural language inputs. The web interface entails different methods to navigate through semantic data sets, including: keyword-based semantic search, graph visualization, faceted interfaces and sentence construction based on natural language.

The user-friendliness of the interface has been a key objective in the design of the environment. In the course of this, the annotations/metadata of the ontology elements play an important role in the presentation of data to the user, as well as in the interpretation of the users' queries. The environment has been validated through their application in the integrated data of the project. However, the prototype environment is generic enough to be applied to multiple domains and cases.

Tools web portal

The SEMANTCO Energy Model as well as the tools developed in the SEMANTCO project are accessible for the research community and the industry in the www.semanco-tools.eu web portal. Documentation, reports, and access to files are provided in the semanco-tools.eu web portal.

The work described in this section has contributed to achieve the following scientific and technological objectives:

- **STO3 Design and implement a semantic-based energy information framework to support decision making related to energy performance in domestic and commercial building stock at different geographical scales.**

The Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF) has been developed within the project for facilitating the energy assessment and analysis tools integrated within the SEMANTCO platform the access to the distributed data sources that hold the data they require. The SEIF deals with different kinds of data at different scales, for example neighbourhood data (e.g. socio-economic data) at urban scale and typologies

(building systems, building properties by age of construction) at building scale. The SEIF, as a key component of the SEMANTCO platform, has been used in the demonstration scenarios where has been confirmed its usefulness and performance on providing integrated access to diverse and heterogeneous data sources.

- STO9 Develop generalised guidelines and recommendations which can be widely applied within urban planning and redevelopment projects

A methodology for building energy models (i.e. ontologies) and integrating data through semantic technologies have been devised within SEMANTCO project. That methodology is a relevant asset for developing systems to support urban planning and redevelopment projects since it can be replicated in other scenarios with other kinds of data sources and user requirements. The methodology, together with the tools developed to support it, is a clear progression beyond the state of the art.

3.4 Integrated platform

The SEMANTCO integrated platform is the front-end for users to interact with the semantic data provided by the Semantic Energy Information Framework. This semantically modelled data (i.e. specified as ontology) represents the combined knowledge of the different experts involved in the definition and solution of a problem concerning the improvement of the energy performance of an urban area. Ontologies also provide access to the multiple data sources from various domains and scales which are needed to formulate and solve a specific problem. The platform, therefore, facilitates access to the knowledge provided by experts – that is, to the methods and tools needed to define and solve a problem– and to the data associated to a specific problem.

The SEMANTCO integrated platform enables the creation of models of urban energy systems which combine energy related data from multiple sources with various energy assessment and simulation tools (Madrazo, Nemirovski & Sicilia, 2013)⁸. For a particular urban area –a city, a district, a neighbourhood– multiple energy models can be created combining data and tools in various ways. Within a given urban model, users can use the tools to assess the energy performance of the urban area, and to carry out plans to improve it. The open structure of the platform enables an urban energy model to be enhanced when new tools and data –either from existing data sources or from the data generated by the different applications– become available (Figure 11).

⁸ Madrazo, L., Nemirovski, G., Sicilia, Á. (2013). Shared Vocabularies to Support the Creation of Energy Urban Systems Models. *Proceedings of the 4th Workshop organised by the EEB Data Models Community ICT for Sustainable Places*, Nice, France, 9-11 September, 2013. Retrieved July 31, 2013 in Web site: http://sustainable-places.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/4thW-eeb_dm_booklet.pdf

Figure 11. Urban energy models created in the platform with data obtained from the SEIF

Both the experts' knowledge captured through the use case methodology (use case and activities templates) as well as the links to the external data sources is available through the SEIF become part of the urban energy models created in the platform.

Platform specifications

The platform has been developed from the specifications derived from the case studies of Manresa (Spain), Newcastle (UK) and Copenhagen (Denmark). By means of a methodology based on use case modelling specifically devised in the project, it has been possible to identify strategic goals regarding carbon reduction in an urban setting in each case, as well as the methods and tools to achieve them. A use case encapsulates the data, tools, activities and users required to address a particular question posed by stakeholders. Use cases are described by means of templates specifically developed for this the project.

The use case methodology has enabled to delimit the scope of the knowledge domains involved to a specific problem (Figure 12). Based on the use case descriptions, urban energy models have been created in the SEMANTCO platform for each of the three cases. External stakeholders (planners, policy makers, consultants) have been involved in the development of the platform, from the description of the use cases to the final testing of the platform functionalities.

Figure 12. A use case as conceptual delimited within case study

Platform structure

The platform has been structured to support the following working process (Figure 13):

1. Creating an urban energy model of an urban area. This implies to define a specific problem case, identify data sources available and the tools that operate with the combined data, and the users from various domains involved in the definition of the problem.
2. Calculating the baseline of an urban energy model. This is done by applying the assessment and simulation tools to the integrated data. This enables users to identify hot spots in areas where interventions to improve building performance is needed.
3. Proposing plans and projects to improve the energy performance of buildings included in the area of the plan. Experts elaborate the plans and the projects. For each urban energy model, multiple plans can be created, and for each plan several projects can be proposed. Improvements brought by plans and projects are calculated using the same tools used to calculate the baseline.
4. Selecting the most appropriate solution to improve the current situation. This is performed with a multi-criteria decision making analysis, which includes the performance indicators of the urban energy model as well as other ad-hoc indicators proposed by the experts.

Figure 13. Work flow of the SEMANCO platform

Three-dimensional geometric modelling

The three-dimensional models of the urban areas are the base of the urban energy models created in the platform. The process to create an urban energy model starts with the construction of a 3d geometric model of the buildings in the urban area using the 3DMaps software. To create a 3d model in 3DMaps the following data was required:

- A DTM (Digital Terrain Model) – this defines the topography, representing the bare ground surface without any objects like plants and buildings.
- A DSM (Digital Surface Model) – this includes all of the permanent features which are above ground. The heights of buildings are commonly extracted from the elevation data within this model.
- A Shape file (.shp) – this is a georeferenced file which contains the footprints and heights of individual buildings. (Geospatial vector data format).

These data has been obtained from different data sources and specific procedures have been devised to create a 3dMaps model from them:

- In the case of Manresa, the base map was created from aerial images and a DSM using the standard 3DMaps tools. A city model was created with the help of a refined cadastre dataset. The original model only contained 2D wall information. To create the 3D model walls were grouped per plot, walls belonging to same plot but with no connection where considered as separate buildings and grouped accordingly. The height of the buildings was derived from the number of floors per building.
- In Copenhagen, the base map was produced from only aerial image since no DSM where available. The city model was created from a Rhinoceros CAD model. The model was exported to KML and imported into Sketchup. In Sketchup the model was geo-referenced manually and grouped on a per building basis for use with 3DMaps. The greater area of Copenhagen where derived from cadastre containing the building footprint and DTM dataset.
- In Newcastle, the base map was created from aerial images and a DSM. The case study area where modelled from a CityGML dataset generated in a LiDAR survey. However the actual model proved to lack information about the separation between dwellings. Because of this the model had to be manually refined in QGIS before it could be used.

In addition, it has been necessary to create ad-hoc solutions to assure the connectivity between the 3dMaps model and the platform tools. In the integration process of the semantic data model and the tools it became necessary to supply additional data derived from the 3D model. URSOS, for example, requires information about wall orientation according to 8 main directions (N, NW, NE, E, W, S, SW, SE). The original 3D format used in 3DMaps can only store information about the building ID. As part of the work of the project, the format was extended to be able to handle additional attributes attached directly to the geometry, such as walls. The base platform was also extended to handle interaction with individual geometry elements. The content pipeline was improved with partial support for exports from Rhinoceros, Revit and Sketchup. Simplified 3D volume modelling capabilities where added to 3DMaps for use with the platform.

Interoperability

In the SEMANTCO project, semantic web technologies have been applied to create open semantic data models consisting of data from multiple sources which communicate with energy assessment tools (Figure 14). Ontologies assure the interoperability in two ways:

- The interoperability among data from multiple domains, sources and applications. This data exchange is controlled by the Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF), which “knows” not only the meaning of the data but where the data is stored.
- The interoperability between the data semantically modelled and the tools that interact with them

Figure 14. Interoperability of data and tools by means of semantic technologies

In this open semantic model, the different layers of data obtained from multiple sources are interlinked to each other via the shared vocabulary (e.g. ontologies). Here, a polygon in a 3D model “knows”, for example, its relation to the information facilitated by the different data sources such as the cadastre, census or climate data. This semantically modelled data also “knows” with which tools it can interact, for example, to perform an energy simulation. The access to the data and tools takes place within the SEMANTCO integrated platform. This enables end-users to apply a variety of tools upon the semantic data is available for a given urban energy model.

The approach adopted in SEMANTCO to facilitate the interoperability between data from multiple sources and domains and the various tools that interact with them represents an alternative to the interoperability based on a single exchange format (e.g. IFC, CityGML). Rather, an alternative approach based on semantic technologies can provide the required flexibility to create and maintain models which incorporate data from various domains and applications and to ensure the interoperability of the data with a set of tools over time. Such semantic-based data models, like the one developed in SEMANTCO, combine the data-centred approach adopted by the open standards with the open demands of interoperability.

To verify the feasibility of this semantic-based solution to interoperability, URSOS – Urban Planning and Sustainability, an existing software to simulate the energy performance of urban areas – has been integrated in the SEMANTCO platform. By means of semantic technologies (i.e. SPARQL queries), the URSOS calculation engine has been fed with data from different data sources (e.g. cadastre, census, building typologies) via the Semantic Energy Information Framework (SEIF) previously developed in the SEMANTCO project.

Integrated tools

The platform integrates building assessment, simulation and analysis tools that interoperate with the semantic data. These tools are used to assess the current energy performance level of the buildings in the urban energy model, to enable the application of measures aimed to improve their performance of buildings and for the quantitative calculation of the results of such interventions, and for the advanced analysis of the data. These tools are the following:

- **SAPMAP** (SAP estimator and decision support tool), based on a simplified Standard Assessment Procedure (SAP) for domestic energy usage used in the UK. It is used to assess the current state of domestic buildings and evaluate the costs and benefits of the possible interventions to improve the current state. It is used to calculate the baseline energy efficiency of individual, pre-existing houses. It

also focuses on establishing a baseline of data allowing for evaluating the effectiveness of potential improvements to those buildings.

- **USiT/USiT-improvement** a tool to simulate the energy performance of urban areas based on the URSOS simulation engine. URSOS is a software tool for assessing and comparing the energy and environmental performance of buildings in an urban area. It has been developed by the Grupo de Energía y Edificación, from the University of Zaragoza (Spain). The program simulates the thermal behaviour of buildings or residential areas according to climate conditions, thermal characteristics of enclosures, ventilation rates and volume. The USiT tool integrated in the platform enables the calculation the current energy performance and assessment of the impact of the measures to improve it. It is an interface between the end-user the URSOS simulation engine, which automatically retrieves the inputs it needs from the urban energy model created in the SEMANCO platform.
- **UEP (Urban Energy Planning tool)/ UEO (Urban Energy Optimization tool).** The UEP tool assesses energy demand and the UEO tool determines the optimal combination of measures to achieve sustainable energy supply and energy savings. The tool produces two major outputs. The first is a “baseline” measurement of the current state of the city. This “baseline” is defined as the quantification of CO₂ emissions based on energy consumption within the city’s defined geographical area for a given year. CO₂ emissions are mapped from energy fuel sources and the respective reduction potentials.
- **Mine-On** (Data Mining Analysis Tools), it facilitates access to data mining processes using RapidMiner / RapidAnalytics technologies. These tools support the decision making process related to energy efficient urban planning. They enable advanced analysis of energy related data at different geographical scales. For instance, at the neighbourhood scale the tools can help to select solutions for building refurbishment and at the municipal scale they can be used to optimise the energy consumption and reduce the CO₂ emissions in a newly planned development. Advanced analysis tools are used for:
 - Data retrieval and data classification, performed on the data integrated in an urban energy model. For instance, classifications of buildings according to their usage (family house, apartment block, educational building, shop, storage, garage, etc.), or year of construction; statistics of energy consumption for each building type, forecasts for energy consumption for selected building classes etc.
 - Statistical data analysis. For example, using numeric regression algorithms (linear regression) for predicting the energy consumption of a certain class of building.
 - Visualising analysis results, in a way that is understandable for the different types of users. Including visualising the results in the 3d model or by means of interactive diagrams and charts.

The data mining is performed with RapidMiner and RapidAnalytics, the data visualization is based on Mondrian and JFreeChart.

- **Multi Criteria Decision Tool**, that enables the comparison of the different plans and projects created to improve the existing conditions of buildings in an urban area. The MCDA tool supports users to select the best solutions to achieve specific targets by enabling the comparison of multiple plans and projects for a given urban area. The MCDA method is not compensatory, so the weights attached to each evaluation criteria denote its absolute importance when considering the desirability of a given project. This value is independent of both the range of possible values of indicators and of the choice of units used to measure them. The user can introduce indicators beyond those concerned with energy such as the social perception of a particular project.

SAPMAP, USiT and UEP are used both to calculate the baselines of an urban energy model and to simulate the improvements achieved adopting measures in specific projects.

Implementation

The development of the platform has run in parallel to its step-by-step implementation in three iterations of the demonstration scenarios carried out in the three cases of study. The feed-back obtained from users participating in these successive implementations has been used to improve its functionalities and further refine

its specifications. In the last demonstration scenarios, a usability test has been performed to verify the functionalities of the final version of the platform (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Final version of the SEMANTCO platform

The work described in this section has contributed to achieve the following scientific and technological objectives:

- STO4 Application of automatic data analysis processes based on semantic relationships to support energy analysis and visualization tools

Advanced analysis using the Mine-On tools in combination with RapidMiner and RapidAnalytics have been performed in the case study of Copenhagen to predict energy consumption from an incomplete dataset. To facilitate user access to these analysis they have been implemented as web services. The outcomes of the analysis have been facilitated in a graphical format to facilitate the understanding to non-experts.

- STO6 Provide verifiable and transparent methods of measuring energy performance. The approach adopted will link together the modelling methods used for performance based energy profiling at the building level and the prescriptive building energy codes used to model building stock at the district and national levels.

The tools used to assess the energy performance, SAPMAP and USiT, are based on the Standard Assessment Procedure adopted in the UK and in the Spanish regulations respectively. The SAPMAP tool has been extensively compared against the results of applying SAP to given buildings and the results found to be close, with no systemic errors. A similar, small scale, test has been conducted for URSOS and it also produces very similar results to the national Spanish methodologies.

- STO7 Integrate and enhance energy analysis, visualization and optimisation tools and techniques in standardised environments enabling stakeholders to work collaboratively.

The SEMANTCO platform facilitates multiple stakeholders to work collaboratively in the processes of defining an urban energy model, determining the current baseline, propose alternatives to improve them and select the most appropriate solution. It provides different visualization modes – 3dmodels, charts,

tables, lists- to facilitate the information in a way that can be easily accessible and understandable to the different user profiles.

3.5 Engaging stakeholders

In the first eighteen months of the project⁹ more than ninety stakeholders in the case study areas were involved in the requirements capture. The outcomes were the identification, specification and validation of a range of Use Cases applicable to Denmark, Spain and the UK. The use cases are described in the form of a detailed specification for the practical application of the ICT tools by a range of stakeholders⁹. The methods used to identify the specific real world problems to be addressed in each use case by the tools developed within the SEMANCO draw on the Multiview methodology. Following this approach the core questions addressed in the requirements capture process, is, *how are the tools and methods of analysing CO₂ reduction in urban design supposed to further the aims of ‘Actors’ and ‘Users’ within the three case study areas?* This ensures that the requirements capture accounts for real-world applications situated within the wider dynamic political economic and social context. Using this approach each use case was designed around a ‘real world problem’ ensuring that the tools developed based on the use cases can address those problems.

Figure 16. Interrelations between requirements capture, technological development and demonstration

The specifications embodied in the use cases produced were used to underpin technical development of the tools, the demonstrations as well as informing the dissemination and exploitation planning of the technologies outputs (Figure 16). In this way the engagement with the stakeholders that took part in the initial requirements capture was built into the IT solutions developed in the project.

To ensure that the SEMANCO tools are applicable beyond the case studies an analysis of how they can be more generally applied was conducted. This was achieved by the mapping of the key parameters relevant to CO₂ reduction and the requirements related to policy, data, stakeholders and technological development in a total of 11 urban development projects in the three case study countries. This research involved face to face interviews with over twenty five professionals involved in the different development projects. This work confirmed the potential applicability of the SEMANCO platform and the tools developed, beyond the three

⁹ These are presented in the appendices of the following Deliverable from the SEMANCO project. Crosbie, T., Crilly, M., Oliveras, J., Gamboa, G., Niwaz, N., Lynch, D. (2013) SEMANCO Deliverable 6.1 *Stakeholder requirements analysis*. Retrieved on January 30, 2014 at http://www.semanco-project.eu/index_htm_files/SEMANCO_D6.1_20130430.pdf

case studies in Newcastle, Manresa and North Harbour. It also provided common set of key parameters that can be used to describe urban development projects.

Stakeholders were also involved in the identification and validation of the business models and strategies developed in the project to support the application of the SEMANTCO platform beyond the three case study areas in Denmark, Spain and the UK. External validation of key elements of the most promising business model (customer segment, value proposition, customer relationships and communication channels) was undertaken with twenty stakeholders. Wider ‘soft-market’ testing was also undertaken via a questionnaire which was circulated to 400 relevant stakeholders and received a 25% response rate. The findings of this validation process not only informed the requirements for commercial exploitation but also provided further recommendations for the technological development of the SEMANTCO platform. The work conducted with stakeholders in relation to the business approach suggested that the most fruitful approach would be to exploit the SEMANTCO platform as a whole, while releasing many of the individual components of the platform as open source. It was agreed that the exploitation root for the platform is via the EECITIES energy services provider. Hence the EECITIES web portal (www.eecities.com) has been created to attract customers and enable SEMANTCO partners to collaborate to provide answers to future customers’ requests (Figure 17).

The SEMANTCO consortium were involved in over forty events to engage stakeholders in the technical development exploitation planning and dissemination. Prominent among these in terms of stakeholder engagement were the three workshops organised in Newcastle, Copenhagen and Manresa toward the end of the project. In total one hundred and thirty people attended the three events from companies, local authorities, universities and charities. The events were highly valuable in terms of disseminating the results of the SEMANTCO project and gaining feedback from participants regarding the utility of the project final outputs.¹⁰

Figure 17. EECITIES web portal

¹⁰ Carpenter, M. (ed.) (2014) SEMANTCO Deliverable 7.5 *Project stakeholder dissemination events*. Retrieved 29.1.15 at http://www.semanco-project.eu/index_htm_files/SEMANTCO_D7.5_20140630.pdf

The work described in this section has contributed to achieve the following scientific and technological objectives:

- STO1 Developing evidence-based quantifiable strategies to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions through ICTs situated within their particular problem domain

In starting with the question “how are the tools and methods of analysing CO₂ reduction in urban design supposed to further the aims of ‘Actors’ and ‘Users’ within the three case study areas the work ensured that the ICT solutions developed were situated within their particular problem domains thus contributing to this objective.

- STO5 Identify ‘energy use hot spots’ at the district level to support the effective targeting of urban energy efficiency and renewable energy interventions. This will involve integrating enhanced tools for visualization and evaluation that access different data sets.

The deployment of the use cases ensured that the tools developed in the project were capable of identifying ‘energy use hot spots’ at the district level to support the effective targeting of urban energy efficiency and renewable energy interventions thus contributing this objective.

- STO9 Develop generalised guidelines and recommendations which can be widely applied within urban planning and redevelopment projects

The work done to provide a common set of key parameters that can be used to describe urban development projects contributed to the development of generalised guidelines and recommendation that can be applied in urban development and redevelopment projects thus contributing to meeting this objective.

3.6 Designing and implementing demonstration scenarios

Demonstration scenarios were designed in each of the three case studies:

- To apply the methods and tools identified in the activities;
- To obtain feedback from users in different settings;
- To provide information to support the technological development of the project.

The demonstration scenarios were implemented in parallel to the project development. At the early implementation phase, each partner selected a preliminary subset of indicators and tools to be used in the three demonstration rounds. Also, the demonstration activities to be carry out at each implementation cycle were in accordance with the current status of the project’s technological achievements. Then, as the technological development progressed, the scenarios have been adapted accordingly (i.e. more indicators, tools and data came in to play as the project progressed).

In order to deal with this cyclical development process, the *implementation*¹¹ and *demonstration*¹² of the SEMANTCO tools and functionalities have been structured in three *demonstration round*. Following the use case methodology each case study scenario (Newcastle, Copenhagen and Manresa) have defined strategic goals regarding carbon reduction in urban settings and the methods and tools to achieve it. According to these strategic goals, partners have developed specific use cases with their corresponding activities, which were then used to translate real requirements into the language of the project (e.g. the SEMANTCO ontology, the urban energy models in the platform).

¹¹ *Implementation* refers to the process of carrying out the sequence of activities considered in a use case either with external, prototype or integrated tools (depending on the state of project development). It encompasses gathering and integrating data, entering data to simulation models, calculating the performance indicators and visualize results.

¹² *Demonstration* refers to the validation of the SEMANTCO decision support tools in terms of their cost effectiveness and capacity to support informed planning decisions that reduce CO₂ emissions in the built environment. Demonstration will take place mostly in the last implementation round, when the SEMANTCO integrated platform is fully operative.

The objectives of each demonstration round relied upon the state of the project development. Accordingly, there goals were the following:

- The **first round** was concerned with integrating data from different sources and the tools for evaluating the energy performance of buildings in an urban area. With this purpose, the requirements of tools and of the technological platform were identified and feedback the technological development was provided.
- The **second round** was about integrating data, tools and users using the prototype version of the integrated platform. The available SEMANCO tools were tested and further feedback was provided to technological development in order to improve the integrated platform.
- The **third round** focused on using and verifying the functionalities of the final version of the SEMANCO platform. Also, a usability test was performed. Feedback to technological development was aimed at providing inputs to fine-tuning the platform, its integrated tools and data.

The purpose of the SEMANCO platform is to supply relevant and qualified information to support decision making in energy efficiency urban planning. This requires that:

- The functionalities of the platform deal with the main challenges identified from a theoretical and methodological point of view. This includes a) Urban energy systems operating at different levels, b) Multiple dimensions to represent urban energy systems, c) Energy transformations across scales and d) Finding a balance between detailed and relevant information.
- The platform provides the users a structured process to meet the strategic goals regarding carbon reduction in urban settings. That is, users have to be able to perform a set of activities defined within each use case and classified as follows: a) Creating alternative urban projects, b) Integrating data from different sources, c) Simulating the energy performance of an urban area and d) Calculating performance indicators and compare projects.
- The results produced by using the tools integrated in the platform are relevant to the users and stakeholders involved in the energy efficient urban planning.

These requirements were successfully evaluated with regard to the final version of the platform.

In the following, the outcomes of the three rounds of demonstrations are presented.

Implementation of the scenarios

In the **first round of demonstrations**, there was a wide diversity of aims, available data and tools across the case studies. Therefore, different use cases have been implemented in each location. However, in general, the three use cases pursue the same objective; namely, *to calculate the energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, costs and /or socio-economic benefits of an urban plan for a new or existing development*. In this first implementation the Semantic Energy Information System (SEIF) and the SEMANCO integrated platform were under development. Therefore, domain experts gathered and integrated data, entered data to simulation models and calculated the performance indicators following the procedures established in the use case. In this way, by implementing the use cases of the three demonstration scenarios, the flows of data and activities defined in each use case were tested and further updated.

In the case of Newcastle, the first round of demonstration succeeded in calculating the energy efficiency performance, the CO₂ emissions and SAP rate of existing single dwellings using a prototype calculation tool. This tool was then integrated in the SEMANCO platform.

In the case of Copenhagen, a baseline of specific energy demands for a set of building typologies was defined. Also, an excel-based tool to calculate the expected energy performance and CO₂ emissions of the target urban area, for the next 10 years, was developed. This tools was also integrated in the integrated platform.

In Manresa, building geometries were manually drawn and introduced into the URSOS software. Also, domain experts estimated and introduced in URSOS the electricity consumption as well as the technical and occupation parameters of buildings. Then, heating and cooling demand of buildings were calculated using that software. During this round of implementation, the calculation procedure of CO₂ emissions was defined by domain experts.

It can be said that indicators related to energy demand and CO₂ emissions are very similar across case studies. Economic issues were considered from the supply side in the North Harbour demonstration scenario, and from the consumption perspective in the other two cases. Not all case studies deal with energy certification issues and there is still a lack of cross-cutting quality of life indicators across cases, with few exception of Newcastle.

As a result of this first round of demonstrations, domain experts had to redefine some of the activities initially considered in the use cases.

The results of the first round were taken into account in the design the second round of demonstrations, which included the calculation a more comprehensive set of energy performance indicators and capturing a set of urban planning indicators.

In the **second round of demonstrations**, users performed the same activities as in the first round but using the SEIF and a prototype of the integrated SEMANTCO platform. The goal of these demonstrations was to check whether the platform, in its current state, provides relevant and qualified information to support energy efficient urban planning. Domain experts adapted the use cases implemented in the first round of demonstrations according to the current state of the platform. Then, several potential users were contacted and asked to carry out the activities within each demonstration scenario. Based on their experience of using the platform, the users were asked about their opinions of the capacity of the platform to provide the information they needed. In parallel, the domain experts who set up the demonstration scenarios evaluated how well the platform enabled the end-users to meet the objectives of the demonstration.

Based on the evaluations of the users and domain experts, feedback was provided to indicate where the tools and the functionalities of the platform needed to be updated. In general, users evaluated whether relevant and useful data was available on the SEMANTCO integrated platform, whether the tools and the set of indicators currently available on the SEMANTCO platform are adequate for supporting their decision-making. The main outcomes of the second round of demonstrations were the following:

- Users considered that the list of existing indicators was incomplete. The missing indicators included urban issues (e.g. population densities, land values), energy performance (e.g. demand of energy carriers according to final energy uses and per square meter) and socio-economic indicators (e.g. internal rate of return or cost of supply technologies).
- The methods offered within the tools integrated in the platform require that the user possesses considerable amounts of technical knowledge. Some users suggested that certain reference values (e.g. U-values of different materials) which could help them in the creation of energy efficient projects should be included.
- Some users had difficulties understanding the parameters of the multicriteria decision making tool, (i.e. weights and thresholds) and consequently in fully using it.
- Users considered that all of the tools for simulating the energy performance of buildings were both relevant and useful for decision making. However, they required some explanations about both the calculation methods and the parameters of the tools.

In the **third round**, users have performed a sequence of tasks similar to those followed in the first two phases of the demonstrations: creating an urban energy model, defining a baseline, analysing a baseline, creating new plans and projects, and evaluating and comparing projects. In addition, usability tests have been conducted by participants from each case study area.

The feedback from all three rounds of the demonstrations suggests that some additional functionalities are required to enhance the user's experiences when using the SEMANTCO platform. Also, users highlighted the need of including tutorials and reference values to make the platform more user friendly and support non-experts users. These issues were addressed in the final review and enhancement of the platform prior to its public release via the EECITIES energy services web-portal.

In the final stage of the demonstrations users in all case studies were, in general, satisfied with the performance of the platform. Users were able to perform the sequence of activities and obtain the information required to address the problem case relevant to them. Also, it was possible to envisage potential users for the EECITIES energy services web-portal in the three study areas:

- In Newcastle the envisaged user would be an energy consultant in charge of proposing strategic energy plans for local authorities as part of an Energy Master Plan. The aim of this strategic energy plan is to prioritise resources to improve the worst performing areas of the city in relation to energy efficiency.
- In Copenhagen, the foreseen user is an urban planner from the municipality assigned the task of evaluating several strategies for energy supply in a ‘greenfield’ project.
- In Manresa the user is meant to be a professional that is not necessarily an expert in planning or energy building performance that needs to identify the most appropriate measures to refurbish a group of buildings in the city.

The findings of the usability tests illustrate that the platform is perceived by potential users as useful, configurable and clear. However, these tests also show that users found that level of difficulty increases when using the embedded tools. Again, this suggests the need to guide users in the process by providing further assistance in the form of user guides and introductory information about the platform structure.

The work described in this section has contributed to achieve the following scientific and technological objectives:

- STO5 Identify ‘energy use hot spots’ at the district level to support the effective targeting of urban energy efficiency and renewable energy interventions. This will involve integrating enhanced tools for visualization and evaluation that access different data sets.

The platform provides the users the baseline information about the energy performance of the target buildings and urban area. Users have been able to visualize this information through both the 3D maps, tables and graphics. During demonstrations, and as part of the implemented use cases, users have been able to test and evaluate the ability of the platform to support the identification of hot spots of poor energy performance. In this regards, the possibility to apply filters in the 3D maps has been considered as an interesting feature to support this task.

The platform also offers information from external data bases on building energy performance (e.g. energy related LLSOA data in the case of Newcastle or building certification data in the case of Manresa), which has been also considered useful by the users.

- STO8 Demonstrate and validate the value of decision support tools in terms of their cost effectiveness and ability to support informed planning decisions that reduce CO₂ emissions from the built environment. This demonstration and validation phase of the research will be conducted in specifically designed scenarios with the end-users within the case studies

One of the most valued features of the platform has been its capacity to integrate data from different and dispersed data sources, and then to use this information to calculate the energy performance of urban areas. This feature enables the user to save huge amount of time compared to performing the same tasks without the platform. For instance, in the Manresa case, domain experts spent much time in drawing the buildings and entering this information to the URSOS software. Now, the building geometry is automatically obtained from the city’s GIS integrated in the SEIF. In the case of Newcastle, the SAP rate of dwellings can be calculated using the platform, which provides similar results than the calculation of the SAP rate performed by experts visiting the building.

- STO10 Increase awareness of the potential of ICT tools to support energy related urban planning

Participants in the three rounds of demonstrations in the three study areas evaluated the platform very positively. They realized that the platform provided easy access to data and to the calculation of the energy performance of buildings and urban areas. This fact clearly increase the awareness of the potential of ICT tools to support energy related urban planning.

4 Use and dissemination of foreground

4.1 Section A

TEMPLATE A1: LIST OF SCIENTIFIC (PEER REVIEWED) PUBLICATIONS, STARTING WITH THE MOST IMPORTANT ONES										
N O.	Title	Main author	Title of the periodical or the series	Number, date or frequency	Publisher	Place of publication	Year of publication	Relevant pages	Permanent identifiers 13 (if available)	Is/Will open access ¹⁴ provided to this publication?
1	MapOn: A Web-Based Editor for Visual ontology Mapping", submitted to the Semantic Web Journal	Alvaro Sicilia, German Nemirovski, Andreas Nolle	Semantic Web Journal				Forthcoming			

¹³ A permanent identifier should be a persistent link to the published version full text if open access or abstract if article is pay per view) or to the final manuscript accepted for publication (link to article in repository).

¹⁴ Open Access is defined as free of charge access for anyone via Internet. Please answer "yes" if the open access to the publication is already established and also if the embargo period for open access is not yet over but you intend to establish open access afterwards.

2	ClickOnA: An approach for integration of domain experts into the ontology design and evaluation process -- Case Study Urban Planning	German Nemirovski, Andreas Nolle, Alvaro Sicilia, Leandro Madrazo	Semantic Web Journal			Forthcoming				
3	Data structuring for the ontological modelling of urban energysystems: The experience of the SEMANTCO project	Vincenzo Corrado, Ilaria Ballarini, Leandro Madrazo, German Nemirovskij	Sustainable Cities and Society	Volume 14	Elsevier	n/a	2015	223-235	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2014.09.006	No
4	Data Integration Driven Ontology Design, Case Study Smart City	German Nemirovskij, Alvaro Sicilia, Andreas Nolle, Ilaria Ballarini, Vincenzo Corrado	Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Web Intelligence, Mining and Semantics 2013 (WIMS 2013)	12th June 2013	ACM	Madrid, Spain	2013	Article No. 43	http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_files/WIMS2013.pdf Also http://porto.polito.it/2517910/	yes
5	An Approach for Accessing Linked Open Data for Data Mining Purposes	Andreas Nolle, German Nemirovski Alvaro Sicilia, Joan Pleguezuelos	Proceedings of the 4th RapidMiner Community Meeting And Conference 2013 (RCOMM 2013)	27th – 30th August 2013	Shaker Verlag	Proto, Portugal	2013	71-78	http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_files/RCOMM2013.pdf Also https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262	yes

									492058_An Approach for Accessing Linked Open Data for Data Mining Purposes	
6	Shared Vocabularies to Support the Creation of Energy Urban Systems Models	Leandro Madrazo, Alvaro Sicilia, German Nemirovski	Proceedings of the 4th Workshop organised by the EEB Data Models Community ICT for Sustainable Places Nice, France, 9th-11th September, 2013	4th annual workshop	Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union	Luxembourg:	2014	130-150?	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/energy-efficiency-building-2-publications-data-models-community-ict-sustainable-places	yes
7	Visualising the 'Big Picture': ICT tools and indicators for urban design	Tracey Crosbie, Michael Crilly	Proceedings of the 1st Workshop organised by the EEB Data Models Community ICT for Sustainable Places Nice, France, 9th-11th September, 2013	1st annual workshop	Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union,	Luxembourg:	2014	11-26	http://sustainable-places.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/1stW-eeb_kpis_booklet.pdf also https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/energy-efficiency-building-2-	yes

									publications -data- models- community- ict- sustainable- places	
8	Efficient Federated Debugging of Lightweight Ontologies	Andreas Nolle, Christian Meilicke, Heiner Stuckenschmidt & German Nemirovski	Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Web Reasoning and Rule Systems 2014 (RR 2014)	09/2014	Springer International Publishing	Athens, Greece	2014	206-215	http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_files/RR2014.pdf Also https://www.researchgate.net/publication/263051384_Efficient_Federated_Debugging_of_Lightweight_Ontologies	yes
9	SEMANTCO: Semantic Tools for Carbon Reduction in Urban Planning	Leandro Madrazo, Álvaro Sicilia, Gonzalo Gamboa	9th European Conference on Product and Process Modelling	07/2012	CRC Press	Reykjavik, Iceland	2012	899-908	http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_files/semanco_3rdWorkshop_datamodel.pdf	yes
10	ELITE: An Entailment-based Federated Query Engine for Complete and	Andreas Nolle, German Nemirovski	Proceedings of the 26th International Workshop on Description Logics 2013 (DL 2013)	07/2013	CEUR Electronic Workshop	Ulm, Germany	2013	854-867	http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_f	yes

	Transparent Semantic Data Integration				Proceedings				<p>iles/DL2013_ELITE.pdf</p> <p>Also http://www.ceur-ws.org/Vol-1014/paper_50.pdf</p> <p>Also http://www.researchgate.net/publication/264514347_ELITE_An_Entailment-based_Federated_Query_Engine_for_Complete_and_Transparent_Semantic_Data_Integration</p>	
11	ClickOnA: An Editor for DL-LiteA based Ontology Design	Michael Wolters, German Nemirovski, Andreas Nolle	Proceedings of the 26th International Workshop on Description Logics 2013 (DL 2013)	07/2013	CEUR Electronic Workshop Proceedings	Ulm, Germany	2013	1000-1010	<p>http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_files/DL2013_ClickOnA.pdf</p> <p>Also http://www.ceur-ws.org/Vol-1014/paper_50.pdf</p>	yes

									1014/paper_62.pdf Also https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264514426_ClickOn_A_An_Editor_for_DL-Lite_A_base_d_Ontology_Design	
12	Implications of open access data for low cost KPIs measuring energy	Martin Carpenter, Tracey Crosbie, Michael Crilly, Nashwan Dawood, Amit Mhalas	The Sustainable Places Conference proceedings October 1-3, 2014 Nice, France	01/10/14	Organizing Committee, of 2nd Sustainable Places International Conference .	Nice France	2014	68-69 abstract only	Abstract available at http://sustainable-places.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/SP14_Proceedings_281014.pdf Full paper available at http://semanco-project.eu/index_html_files/UoT_IC_T_SPlaces2014_PostReview_08_08.pdf	Yes

TEMPLATE A2: LIST OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

NO.	Type of activities ¹⁵	Main leader	Title	Date/Period	Place	Type of audience ¹⁶	Size of audience	Countries addressed
1	Workshop	POLITO	Network meeting about Smart Cities projects	Nov 2014	Torino	Scientific Community	15	Europe
2	Exhibition	FORUM	The most relevant outputs of the SEMANTCO demonstrations held in Manresa were presented by FORUM answering a request from the Councilor of Environment of the Manresa Municipality	Nov 2014	Manresa	Policy makers	2	Spain
3	Exhibition	FORUM	To briefly (10 minutes) present the SEMANTCO project in an event organised by another EU project named SUSTAINCO (http://www.sustainco.info/es/links), which focuses on nZEB concept	Nov 2014	Manresa	Industry	30	Spain
4	Exhibition	FUNITEC	Smart City Expo World Congress	Nov 2014	Barcelona	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	100	Europe
5	Exhibition	CIMNE	Presentation of the SEMANTCO platform during a session on 'How to promote "nearly" Zero-energy buildings for new and retrofitting buildings in the	Oct 2014	Barcelona	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers,	150	Europe

¹⁵ A drop down list allows choosing the dissemination activity: publications, conferences, workshops, web, press releases, flyers, articles published in the popular press, videos, media briefings, presentations, exhibitions, thesis, interviews, films, TV clips, posters, Other.

¹⁶ A drop down list allows choosing the type of public: Scientific Community (higher education, Research), Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Medias, Other ('multiple choices' is possible).

			municipal context' at the WSB14 conference			Scientific Community		
6	Exhibition	NEA	NEA Annual Conference	Sept 2014	Scarborough	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers,	250	UK
7	Exhibition	FUNITEC, FORUM	Meeting with a representative from the city of Barcelona in order to discuss the possibility of adapting and using SEMANTCO in the city of Barcelona.	Sept 2014	Barcelona	Policy makers	1	Spain
8	Workshop	UoT	2nd International Symposium on Energy Challenges and Mechanics	Aug 2014	Aberdeen	Scientific Community	100	UK
9	Exhibition	NEA	NEA Fuel Poverty Forum	Jul 2014	Nottingham, UK	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers,	40	UK
10	Exhibition	NEA	NEA Business Supporter Group meeting	July 2014	Newcastle	Industry	~30	UK
11	Exhibition	UoT	Presented at the TFI Annual Research Day, an major internal research event at the UoT	June 2014	Middlesbrough	Scientific Community	105	UK
12	Exhibition	FUNITEC	Presentation to the European Construction Technology Platform 6th Conference.	June 2014	Brussels	Scientific Community	N/A	Europe
13	Exhibition	FORUM	A non-scientific engagement of children and parents as part of Sustainable Energy Week	June 2014	Manresa	Civil Society	~25 children + parents	Spain
14	Workshop	FORUM	One of the SEMANTCO organised stakeholder events to evaluate the projects progress. See Deliverable 7.5 <i>Project Stakeholder Dissemination Events</i>	May 2014	Manresa	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	43	Spain
15	Workshop	NEA	A major SEMANTCO stakeholder event held to evaluate the projects progress. See Deliverable 7.5 <i>Project Stakeholder Dissemination Events</i>	May 2014	Newcastle	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	42	UK
16	Workshop	Ramboll	A major SEMANTCO stakeholder event held to evaluate the projects progress. See Deliverable 7.5 <i>Project Stakeholder Dissemination Events</i>	May 2014	Copenhagen	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers,	42	Denmark

						Scientific Community		
17	Exhibition	CIMNE	II Congress in nZEB	May 2014	Madrid	Scientific Community	100	Spain
18	Exhibition	FUNITEC	11th Extended Semantic Web Conference	May 2014	Anissaras, Greece	Scientific Community	30	Europe
19	Exhibition	NEA	Ecobuild is the biggest event in the world for sustainable design, construction and the built environment.	Mar 2014	London	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	44,500	UK (Europe)
20	Exhibition	NEA	Green build expo. Exhibition stand, entry into awards opportunity to present SEMANTCO directly.	Mar 2014	Manchester	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	4000	UK
21	Workshop	FORUM	Meeting with an EPSEM representative.	Mar 2014	Manresa	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers	1	Spain
22	Exhibition	NEA	Evening reception in the House of Lords	Mar 2014	London	Civil Society, Policy makers,	200	UK
23	Workshop	FORUM	Meeting with secretary of the urban planners architects association of Catalonia	Feb 2014	Manresa	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers	1	Spain
24	Workshop	FORUM	Meeting with PIREEB representatives	Feb 2014	Manresa	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers	5	Spain
25	Workshop	FUNITEC, CIMNE, POLITO and HAS	4 th Vocabulary Camp (VoCamp) on “Integrating multiple domains and scales”. Organised by SEMANTCO.	Feb 2014	Barcelona	Scientific Community	33	Europe
26	Other	FUNITEC	Presentation of SEMANTCO to KIC-InnoEnergy in the hope of gaining support to make it into a marketable solution.	Feb 2014	Barcelona	Industry	N/A	Europe
27	Workshop	UoT	Conference presentation with accompanying paper and workshop discussion on “Visualising Complexity &	Jan 2014	Manchester	Industry, Civil Society,	50	UK

			Precautionary Planning". (Crilly <i>et al</i> 2014) Part of the 12 th meeting of AESOP - Confronting Urban Planning and Design with Complexity: Methods for Inevitable Transformation			Scientific Community		
28	Exhibition	FUNITEC, FORUM	FUNITEC and FORUM presented the project and the platform to a group of representatives from the Catalan Institute of Energy during a technical meeting held with the purpose of gathering information from them to feed the platform.	Jan 2014	Barcelona	Industry	5	Spain
29	Exhibition	FORUM	Presentation of SEMANTCO to two regular meetings of the AVS association	Oct, Dec 2013	Manresa	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers,	30 for both meetings combined	Spain
30	Exhibition	Several SEMANTCO partners including Rambol, NEA and FUNITEC	ICT2013 event. SEMANTCO had an exhibition space at the event to disseminate technical developments and outputs from the tool. Leaflets and video still images were shared at the event to raise the profile of the programme.	Nov 2013	Vilnius, Lithuania	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	4000	Europe
31	Exhibition	FUNITEC, UoT	Presentation of SEMANTCO as an invited speaker at the ConvVR conference held in London.	Oct 2013	London	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	100	UK
32	Presentation of the project	HAS	Presentation of SEMANTCO tools in the research colloquium of the university of Mannheim, Data and Web Science Group (Data and Web Science Groupmembers of the University of Mannheim,)	Sept 2013	Mannheim	Scientific Community	N/A	Germany
33	Exhibition	NEA	NEA Annual Conference	Sept 2013	Scarborough	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers,	~250	UK

34	Workshop	UoT	Presentation on 'Retrofit a whole systems approach' (Crilly 2013b) to low energy refurbishment.	Sept 2013	Leicester	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	50	UK
35	Workshop	Ramboll	SEMANTCO evaluation Workshop with Copenhagen Municipality, Copenhagen Energy, Copenhagen City & Port Development and Region Zealand.	June 2013	Denmark	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers	7	Denmark
36	Exhibition	HAS	SEMCity 13 conference	June 2013	Madrid	Scientific Community	200	Europe
37	Workshop	NEA, UoT	A presentation to NEA's business support group	May 2013	Seven oaks UK	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers	30	UK
38	Exhibition	NEA	Green build expo 2013	May 2013	Manchester	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	4000	UK
39	Workshop	UoT	Presentation on "Adding Value through design Guidance" and the role of decision-support tools in master planning to RTPi Conference, Newcastle upon Tyne	May 2013	Newcastle	Industry, Scientific Community	50	UK
40	Exhibition	NEA	NEA Business Supporter Group meeting	May 2013	Newcastle	Industry	~30	UK
41	Exhibition	CIMNE	18 th Construmat, Power point presentation describing SEMANTCO given	May 2013	Barcelona	Industry, Civil Society, Policy makers, Scientific Community	50	Europe (and outside)
42	Workshop	NEA	IREEN Coordination Day, Amsterdam	May 2013	Amsterdam	Scientific Community	40	Europe
43	Workshop	UoT, Funitec, NEA, Forum, CIMNE,	"Analysing and Visualising Energy Related Data in our Buildings, Towns and Cities" Hosted and organised by SEMANTCO	April 2013	Barcelona	Scientific Community	38 from 16 European projects	Europe

4.2 Section B (Confidential¹⁷ or public: confidential information to be marked clearly)

4.2.1 Part B1

TEMPLATE B1: LIST OF APPLICATIONS FOR PATENTS, TRADEMARKS, REGISTERED DESIGNS, ETC.					
Type of IP Rights ¹⁸ :	Confidential Click on YES/NO	Foreseen embargo date dd/mm/yyyy	Application reference(s) (e.g. EP123456)	Subject or title of application	Applicant (s) (as on the application)

4.2.2 Part B2

¹⁷ Note to be confused with the "EU CONFIDENTIAL" classification for some security research projects.

¹⁸ A drop down list allows choosing the type of IP rights: Patents, Trademarks, Registered designs, Utility models, Others.

Type of Exploitable Foreground ¹⁹	Description of exploitable foreground	Confidential Click on YES/NO	Foreseen embargo date dd/mm/yyyy	Exploitable product(s) or measure(s)	Sector(s) of application ²⁰	Timetable, commercial or any other use	Patents or other IPR exploitation (licences)	Owner & Other Beneficiary(s) involved
	<i>Ex: New superconductive Nb-Ti alloy</i>			<i>MRI equipment</i>	<i>1. Medical 2. Industrial inspection</i>	<i>2008 2010</i>	<i>A materials patent is planned for 2006</i>	<i>Beneficiary X (owner) Beneficiary Y, Beneficiary Z, Poss. licensing to equipment manuf. ABC</i>
Commercial exploitation of R&D results	SEMANCO integrated platform	NO	N/A	The complete demonstrator produced by the SEMANCO project	Urban planning	Currently available	IPR agreements will be made between the partners as agreed	The SEMANCO consortium
General advancement of knowledge	SEIF – the ontology integration software developed in SEMANCO,	No	N/A	Software and supporting methodologies /techniques required to make it work. See entries immediately below for various related bits of software developed	Computer Science	n/a	n/a	To be made publically available to the scientific community as open source software In addition, descriptions of many core scientific ideas will be publicised via appropriate scientific publications

¹⁹ A drop down list allows choosing the type of foreground: General advancement of knowledge, Commercial exploitation of R&D results, Exploitation of R&D results via standards, exploitation of results through EU policies, exploitation of results through (social) innovation.

²⁰ A drop down list allows choosing the type sector (NACE nomenclature) : http://ec.europa.eu/competition/mergers/cases/index/nace_all.html

Type of Exploitable Foreground ¹⁹	Description of exploitable foreground	Confidential Click on YES/NO	Foreseen embargo date dd/mm/yyyy	Exploitable product(s) or measure(s)	Sector(s) of application ²⁰	Timetable, commercial or any other use	Patents or other IPR exploitation (licences)	Owner & Other Beneficiary(s) involved
General advancement of knowledge	energy data standardisation protocols	No	-	Protocols for developing ontologies fully usable in conjunction with the seif.	Computer Science	n/a	n/a	To be made publically available to the scientific community through the medium of appropriate scientific publications
General advancement of knowledge	Click-On (Ontology editing tool)	No	-	Software – related to the SEIF	Computer Science	-	-	To be released under LGPL or similar
General advancement of knowledge	Map-On (Ontology mapping tool)	No	-	Software - related to the SEIF	Computer Science	-	-	To be released under LGPL or similar
General advancement of knowledge, Exploitation of R&D results via standards	SAPMAP - Tool/methodology for evaluating energy efficiency of buildings without visiting them	No	-	Software and methodology produced during SEMANCO.	Energy efficiency of housing		-	Software planned to be released as open source, methodology released via relevant papers/deliverables.
General advancement of knowledge	ELITE (Federation Engine)	No	-	Software	Computer Science	-	-	Hoped to be released as open source, dependency on a piece of software may

4.2.3 The exploitable foreground of the SEMANTCO Project

The purpose of the exploitable foreground

The SEMANTCO integrated platform provides access to widely dispersed energy related data about cities stored by many different organisations. In this way the project platform supports improved energy analysis based on the assessment of existing data rather than estimates. It does this using semantic data modelling that enables information stored in different formats and different places to be used to create a multi-level energy model of an urban area. That can be used to analyse the energy performance of buildings, neighbourhoods, districts and regions.

How the foreground might be exploited, when and by whom

The research and development work conducted during the SEMANTCO project has produced numerous potentially exploitable assets. Each of these assets might be exploited in two ways:

- As part of the SEMANTCO integrated platform, which combines all of the assets developed during the project into a cohesive whole.
- As stand-alone products.

In order to retain both potential commercial exploitation and support future research work, the consortium has decided to follow a twin pronged strategy. This involves considering the commercial exploitation of the SEMANTCO integrated platform as a whole, while releasing many of the individual components of the platform as open source.

In order to support the potential commercial exploitation of the SEMANTCO integrated platform a customer facing web portal, EECITIES, has been developed. This portal is developed in Task 5.8 Energy service platform web portal. It is designed to present the results of the SEMANTCO project in a way which will attract potential customers and provide those customers access to the services supported by the SEMANTCO integrated platform. In this way it provides a gateway for the potential future commercial exploitation of the SEMANTCO platform. The customers that might be interested in using the SEMANTCO platform include Municipalities, Energy companies, Property management companies, Technology companies, Sustainability consultancies, Professional institutions, Research organisations and Charity/community groups.

IPR exploitable measures taken or intended

As mentioned earlier many of the assets produced in the SEMANTCO project can be exploited as stand-alone software, or as components of the SEMANTCO integrated platform. Many of the legal concerns arising from this were considered at the outset of the project. They are therefore included within the SEMANTCO Consortium Agreement. This outlines ownership and sharing of both background and foreground. The background IPR that is brought into the project will always remain the property of the partner involved. Those partners making available pre-existing know-how during the course of the project have specified any conditions for access thereto in the Consortium Agreement.

Specifically the Consortium Agreement sets out the following rules:

- Foreground shall be the property of the beneficiary carrying out the work generating that foreground.
- Where several beneficiaries have jointly carried out work generating foreground and where their respective share of the work cannot be ascertained, they shall have joint ownership of such foreground. They shall establish an agreement regarding the allocation and terms of exercising that joint ownership.

In response, if an IP asset is agreed as being of “joint ownership” then one of the Partners can use this asset and sell it to 3rd party, but “with reasonable compensation to the other joint owners”. The SEMANTCO consortium have defined all individual assets produced during the project and assigned them the correct IPR ownership in a manner that conforms to the Consortium Agreement.

In addition the assets developed during the project that have IPR allowing them to be freely distributed by the members of the SEMANTCO consortium, and which do not have also been identified. It has been agreed by the

consortium that nearly all of the individual outputs of the SEMANTCO project will be released under open source licences, therefore there is no need to assign IPR to individual partners.

The IPR ownership over the individual items within the SEMANTCO integrated platform will become relevant if the combined platform itself is exploited in either a commercial manner, or a future research project. The following lists the four main possibilities for the future exploitation of the platform:

1. Someone wishes to exploit the SEMANTCO platform but first requires that the set of calculation methodologies in the platform is extended/ modified.
2. Someone wishes to exploit the SEMANTCO platform but requires a new set of 3D buildings be added to the platform first.
3. Someone wishes to directly exploit the SEMANTCO platform without modification.
4. Research based exploitation of, perhaps part of, the SEMANTCO platform.

The first of the above scenarios might typically occur if someone from a country not already in the SEMANTCO platform wished to try and exploit it in their country. It also covers situations where additional calculation methods were desired in an existing country. The second might happen, if for instance, someone wished to exploit the SEMANTCO platform for Middlesbrough instead of Newcastle, or even to simply extend it to cover all of Newcastle. In the case of each scenario the partners that would need to be involved have been identified

Further research

There is a possibility for the exploitation of the entire platform through research projects rather than as commercial software. In this case the proposed exploitation, while unlikely to involve all of the project partners, would again have to be discussed and agreed on by the SEMANTCO consortium. The individual components of the platform could also be extended in future research projects. To do so the individual project partner(s) responsible for their creation are free under the terms of the Consortium Agreement to build these into future research funding applications.

Potential/expected impact

The SEMANTCO platform could inform future EU and national policy development. If energy models are developed for a large number of cities in different EU countries and the data analysed using the tools in the SEMANTCO platform, it will be possible to make comparisons across countries. This will help policy makers to see how different regulatory regimes impact on the potential for implementing CO₂ friendly measures whereas providing clear evidence for understanding how EU and national policy development can strengthen the transition towards low carbon towns and cities.

4.3 Report on societal implications

A General Information <i>(completed automatically when Grant Agreement number is entered).</i>	
Grant Agreement Number:	287534
Title of Project:	SEMANTCO
Name and Title of Coordinator:	Dr. Leandro Madrazo
B Ethics	
1. Did your project undergo an Ethics Review (and/or Screening)?	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If Yes: have you described the progress of compliance with the relevant Ethics Review/Screening Requirements in the frame of the periodic/final project reports? 	0Yes 0No

Special Reminder: the progress of compliance with the Ethics Review/Screening Requirements should be described in the Period/Final Project Reports under the Section 3.2.2 'Work Progress and Achievements'		
2. Please indicate whether your project involved any of the following issues (tick box) :		YES
RESEARCH ON HUMANS		
• Did the project involve children?		no
• Did the project involve patients?		no
• Did the project involve persons not able to give consent?		no
• Did the project involve adult healthy volunteers?		no
• Did the project involve Human genetic material?		no
• Did the project involve Human biological samples?		no
• Did the project involve Human data collection?		no
RESEARCH ON HUMAN EMBRYO/FOETUS		
• Did the project involve Human Embryos?		no
• Did the project involve Human Foetal Tissue / Cells?		no
• Did the project involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells (hESCs)?		no
• Did the project on human Embryonic Stem Cells involve cells in culture?		no
• Did the project on human Embryonic Stem Cells involve the derivation of cells from Embryos?		no
PRIVACY		
• Did the project involve processing of genetic information or personal data (eg. health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)?		no
• Did the project involve tracking the location or observation of people?		no
RESEARCH ON ANIMALS		
• Did the project involve research on animals?		no
• Were those animals transgenic small laboratory animals?		no
• Were those animals transgenic farm animals?		no
• Were those animals cloned farm animals?		no
• Were those animals non-human primates?		no
RESEARCH INVOLVING DEVELOPING COUNTRIES		
• Did the project involve the use of local resources (genetic, animal, plant etc)?		no
• Was the project of benefit to local community (capacity building, access to healthcare, education etc)?		no
DUAL USE		
• Research having direct military use		no
• Research having the potential for terrorist abuse		no
C Workforce Statistics		
3. Workforce statistics for the project: Please indicate in the table below the number of people who worked on the project (on a headcount basis).		
Type of Position	Number of Women	Number of Men
Scientific Coordinator	2	5
Work package leaders	1	5
Experienced researchers (i.e. PhD holders)	3	25
PhD Students	0	3
Other	9	18
4. How many additional researchers (in companies and universities) were recruited specifically for this project?	8	
Of which, indicate the number of men:	5	

D Gender Aspects		
5. Did you carry out specific Gender Equality Actions under the project?	<input type="radio"/> x	Yes No
6. Which of the following actions did you carry out and how effective were they?		
	Not at all effective	Very effective
<input type="checkbox"/> Design and implement an equal opportunity policy	○ ○ ○ ○ ○	○ ○ ○ ○ ○
<input type="checkbox"/> Set targets to achieve a gender balance in the workforce	○ ○ ○ ○ ○	○ ○ ○ ○ ○
<input type="checkbox"/> Organise conferences and workshops on gender	○ ○ ○ ○ ○	○ ○ ○ ○ ○
<input type="checkbox"/> Actions to improve work-life balance	○ ○ ○ ○ ○	○ ○ ○ ○ ○
<input type="radio"/> Other: <input style="width: 200px;" type="text"/>		
7. Was there a gender dimension associated with the research content – i.e. wherever people were the focus of the research as, for example, consumers, users, patients or in trials, was the issue of gender considered and addressed?		
<input type="radio"/> Yes- please specify <input style="width: 150px;" type="text"/>		
<input checked="" type="radio"/> No		
E Synergies with Science Education		
8. Did your project involve working with students and/or school pupils (e.g. open days, participation in science festivals and events, prizes/competitions or joint projects)?		
<input type="radio"/> Yes- please specify <input style="width: 150px;" type="text"/>		
<input checked="" type="radio"/> No		
9. Did the project generate any science education material (e.g. kits, websites, explanatory booklets, DVDs)?		
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes- please specify <input style="width: 150px;" type="text"/>		
<input type="radio"/> No		
F Interdisciplinarity		
10. Which disciplines (see list below) are involved in your project?		
<input type="radio"/> Main discipline ²¹ : Civil engineering (2.1)		
<input type="radio"/> Associated discipline ²¹ : Computer sciences (1.1)	<input type="radio"/>	Associated discipline ²¹ : Social sciences (5.4)
G Engaging with Civil society and policy makers		
11a Did your project engage with societal actors beyond the research community? (if 'No', go to Question 14)	<input checked="" type="radio"/> ○	Yes No
11b If yes, did you engage with citizens (citizens' panels / juries) or organised civil society (NGOs, patients' groups etc.)?		
<input type="radio"/> No		
<input type="radio"/> Yes- in determining what research should be performed		
<input type="radio"/> Yes - in implementing the research		
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes, in communicating /disseminating / using the results of the project		

²¹ Insert number from list below (Frascati Manual).

11c In doing so, did your project involve actors whose role is mainly to organise the dialogue with citizens and organised civil society (e.g. professional mediator; communication company, science museums)?	<input type="radio"/> <input checked="" type="radio"/>	Yes No
12. Did you engage with government / public bodies or policy makers (including international organisations)		
<input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Yes- in framing the research agenda <input type="radio"/> Yes - in implementing the research agenda <input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes, in communicating /disseminating / using the results of the project		
13a Will the project generate outputs (expertise or scientific advice) which could be used by policy makers?		
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Yes – as a primary objective (please indicate areas below- multiple answers possible) <input type="radio"/> Yes – as a secondary objective (please indicate areas below - multiple answer possible) <input type="radio"/> No		
13b If Yes, in which fields?		
Agriculture Audiovisual and Media Budget Competition Consumers Culture Customs Development Economic and Monetary Affairs Education, Training, Youth Employment and Social Affairs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Energy Enlargement Enterprise <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environment External Relations External Trade Fisheries and Maritime Affairs Food Safety Foreign and Security Policy Fraud Humanitarian aid	Human rights Information Society Institutional affairs Internal Market Justice, freedom and security Public Health Regional Policy Research and Innovation Space Taxation Transport

13c If Yes, at which level? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Local / regional levels <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National level <input type="checkbox"/> European level <input type="checkbox"/> International level		
H Use and dissemination		
14. How many Articles were published/accepted for publication in peer-reviewed journals?	1	
To how many of these is open access²² provided?		
How many of these are published in open access journals?		
How many of these are published in open repositories?		
To how many of these is open access not provided?		
Please check all applicable reasons for not providing open access:		
<input type="checkbox"/> publisher's licensing agreement would not permit publishing in a repository <input type="checkbox"/> no suitable repository available <input type="checkbox"/> no suitable open access journal available <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> no funds available to publish in an open access journal <input type="checkbox"/> lack of time and resources <input type="checkbox"/> lack of information on open access <input type="checkbox"/> other ²³ :		
15. How many new patent applications ('priority filings') have been made? <i>("Technologically unique": multiple applications for the same invention in different jurisdictions should be counted as just one application of grant).</i>		
16. Indicate how many of the following Intellectual Property Rights were applied for (give number in each box).	Trademark	2
	Registered design	2
	Other	
17. How many spin-off companies were created / are planned as a direct result of the project? <i>Indicate the approximate number of additional jobs in these companies:</i>		
18. Please indicate whether your project has a potential impact on employment, in comparison with the situation before your project: <input type="checkbox"/> Increase in employment, or <input type="checkbox"/> Safeguard employment, or <input type="checkbox"/> Decrease in employment, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Difficult to estimate / not possible to quantify	<input type="checkbox"/> In small & medium-sized enterprises <input type="checkbox"/> In large companies <input type="checkbox"/> None of the above / not relevant to the project	
19. For your project partnership please estimate the employment effect resulting directly from your participation in Full Time Equivalent (FTE = one person working fulltime for a year) jobs:	<i>Indicate figure:</i> <input type="checkbox"/>	
Difficult to estimate / not possible to quantify		

I Media and Communication to the general public	
20. As part of the project, were any of the beneficiaries professionals in communication or media relations?	
<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="radio"/> No
21. As part of the project, have any beneficiaries received professional media / communication training / advice to improve communication with the general public?	
<input type="radio"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="radio"/> No
22 Which of the following have been used to communicate information about your project to the general public, or have resulted from your project?	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Press Release <input type="checkbox"/> Media briefing <input type="checkbox"/> TV coverage / report <input type="checkbox"/> Radio coverage / report <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brochures /posters / flyers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DVD /Film /Multimedia	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coverage in specialist press <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coverage in general (non-specialist) press <input type="checkbox"/> Coverage in national press <input type="checkbox"/> Coverage in international press <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Website for the general public / internet <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Event targeting general public (festival, conference, exhibition, science café)
23 In which languages are the information products for the general public produced?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Language of the coordinator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other language(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> English

²² Open Access is defined as free of charge access for anyone via Internet.

²³ For instance: classification for security project.